

Running Head: GLOBALIZATION ON BUSINESS STRATEGIES

THE CHALLENGES OF GLOBALIZATION ON BUSINESS STRATEGIES IN MODERN
ORGANIZATION—A CASE STUDY OF THE AMAZON BUSINESS

by

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WE, THE UNDERSIGNED MEMBERS OF THE COMMITTEE,
HAVE APPROVED THIS DISSERTATION

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Abstract

The study sought to examine the challenges of globalization on the business strategies in the modern organization: a case study of the Amazon. The four objectives guided the study; (a) To establish the relationship between financial globalization and business strategies in Amazon, (b) To set the relationship between technological globalization and the business strategies of Amazon, (c) To assess the effect of financial globalization on business strategies, and (d) To identify the different business strategies used by Amazon. This study adopted a descriptive approach and cross-sectional research designs, which are helpful when a researcher seeks to elicit a participant's experiences, perceptions, and the meanings they attach to them. Data were quantitatively and qualitatively collected, presented, and analyzed. The researcher sent 111 questionnaires electronically via surveymonkey.com to be filled out and were returned from the participants chosen from different level managers and employees of Amazon and from other departments and business units, including Amazon Web Services, Worldwide consumer, Amazon Devices and Digital Management, Amazon Videos and studios, and Amazon robotics.

Data collected were processed and analyzed using MS Excel and SPSS. Findings from the study revealed that there existed a weak positive correlation between economic globalization and business strategies used by Amazon ($p < .398$, $n = 111$, $r = .081$), a very weak positive correlation between technological globalization business strategy ($p < .028$, $n = 111$, $r = .081$), and a consolidative correlation between financial globalization and business strategies in the Amazon ($p < .00$, $n = 111$, $r = .355$). It was, therefore, concluded that of the three measurements of globalization, only financial globalization causes a strong positive effect on business strategies used by Amazon. So, challenges of economic globalization affect the business strategy of an

organization. The study recommends that Amazon should focus on the economic globalization challenges by opening up avenues for new investors to invest in Amazon, among others.

Dedication

I dedicate this dissertation to my dad Hon. Martin Ogola Adada, who invested in my education, constantly asked me to pursue higher education to the highest level possible, and always encouraged me; special thanks to my mum Mrs. Sarah A Ogola, for her continued moral, material, psychological, and financial support toward this academic achievement. Special thanks also go out to my loving wife, Mrs. Agnes Mbuya, and our babies Teysha Samsons and Kyrie Kenan. Finally, to all my brothers and sisters, thank you for the support.

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Chapter 1

Introduction to the Study

From a modest online bookshop to several commercial industries, Amazon has expanded its company. As a result, it has evolved into one of the most significant online retailers as an e-commerce exploiter. Amazon has risen to the top of the global e-commerce market because of its excellent customer relationship management, information technology (IT), and other business methods, as well as an effective supply chain management system. Amazon has found more markets as a result of globalization, yet globalization and the rise of the e-commerce business have also presented obstacles to Amazon. As a result, this study aimed to determine the challenges of globalization on the business strategies of Amazon.

Background of the Study

Globalization is a worldwide trend in which economies lose their borders and become more interconnected. Companies are no longer bound by national boundaries and can engage in a wide range of global business operations. Many businesses operate in international marketplaces, sourcing their raw materials or conducting research and development. As a result, commerce barriers are eroding, and global trade in commodities and services is rising faster than domestic production (Cullen & Parboteeah, 2010).

The primary stream of globalization is the production and marketing of goods and services, in which firms seek out suppliers of goods and services from all over the world to capitalize on national disparities in price and quality of production components. Companies do this to lower total costs and, as a result, improve the quality and functionality of their product in the global village (Levitt, 2014).

Globalization is more precisely defined as the process through which the globe's economies are combined into a single, collaborative entity. Advances in information and communication technology, particularly innovative technology and phone communications, have radically altered the global economy. For example, e-commerce uses technology by firms to provide its products and services to customers in remote regions more conveniently and cost-effectively. The sale and purchase of goods and services over the Internet are known as e-commerce (Aydin & Savrul, 2014).

Previous studies have discovered that money flows more freely across national borders, and businesses are hoping for effective financing rates worldwide, while investors seek a greater return on investment. As a result, from an economic standpoint, globalization facilitates the movement of capital, labor, migration, and technological dissemination; all these things add up to higher company productivity and long-term profit (Lee et al., 2016).

To describe fully globalization, it is necessary to look at the economic effects and the inflow of new information, capital, and labor from different countries. This further integration allows for even more extensive international trade and growth. In addition, the reduction of trade barriers heightened competitiveness across national borders, forcing businesses to devise cost-cutting tactics that take advantage of cross-border opportunities (Candee & Larson, 2013).

The use of technology to globalize markets has facilitated the merging of historically distinct and separate national marketplaces into a giant global market. However, consumer tastes and inclinations fluctuate among regions and nations, making it impossible for businesses to ascertain whether they should sell standardized products globally entirely. In this example, they can benefit from a substantial portion of the global market and thus economies of scale (Muroyama & Stever, 1988).

In their study on risk management and internalization, (Rodriguez et al., 2010) found that international diversification is a strategic choice for enterprises that want and attain sustainable competitive advantage and boost sales and market shares in other nations and regions. In addition, they found that the more diverse the international landscape, the better it will deal with the problems associated with globalization. Unfortunately, the vast majority of diversification initiatives fail to live up to their expected benefits.

Globalization increases the prevalence of opportunities for companies that are more involved in global trade, according to a study conducted on international trade and trade barriers in Canada. As a result, managers of such companies must develop and adopt internationalization strategies to transform their organizations into globally competitive e-businesses. They must also manage supply, production, marketing, and other activities under international market conditions (Nieminen et al., 2016).

About the initial submission, a global organization is a problem that necessitates strategic positioning, organizational abilities, a high degree of coordination and integration, attention to particular market needs, and the adoption of standard processes. In an international setting, strategy refers to an organization's plan for gaining a competitive advantage over its competitors (Porter, 2014).

In economics, internationalization is defined as a process in which businesses become more involved in international markets. The struggle for survival in the global market, ongoing pressure, and the need to maintain and strengthen market position compel organizations to innovate constantly and investigate prospects for gaining a competitive advantage and expanding commercial activities outside the domestic market (Susman, 1984).

The most common global markets are not for mass consumer goods because there are still significant differences between countries in terms of tastes and preferences, which have great significance and act as a brake on globalization, but for industrial goods and materials, which are in universal demand around the world. Because different countries have varied likes and interests, and there is a severe rivalry because of international trade and foreign direct investment, marketing methods are becoming more technical as a result of globalization (Ferreira-Lopes & Van Rompay-Bartels, 2020).

Because of Amazon's general cost leadership and lack of product differentiation, its business model has been imitated by competitors in a brutal price war that has hurt everyone. Furthermore, because its focus is on cost reduction over product differentiation means that its products are available on other portals as well, and no product line is unique and provides gratification to the customer; it is difficult to achieve global recognition because all customers on a global market level are satisfied (Fildes & Perlet, 2020). On this note, a study of the challenges of globalization on business strategies using Amazon as a case study was done.

Statement of the Problem

Globalization is a natural process that arises from the generalization of the nature and method of production, which is a developing and faster process. The advancement of science and technology and the globalization of markets for goods and services have resulted in the internationalization and globalization of economic and financial developments. Globalization is defined as a process that leads to the greater economic integration of national economies, fragmentation of the world economy, and the international economy. It is also defined as opening national economies by removing economic and financial boundaries and transforming them into a global economic and financial maze (Jovanovski et al., 2015).

Because of globalization, companies operate in a global village, characterized by solid competition, pressure, and challenges to keep a competitive edge. As a plan to penetrate the market and optimize sales, the corporation must lower the prices of goods and services in the long run. In addition, enterprises operating in other lands confront fierce competition from indigenous companies manufacturing identical items and various political and social problems as a result of the global perspective of the market (Theodore, 2014).

Amazon is a significant online business and e-commerce leader, with a global focus on customer pleasure and a wide choice of products. Still, according to (LeBlanc, 2020), there has been a lack of product differentiation in the industry. Competitors have created identical products in this situation, posing a marketing challenge for Amazon regarding consumer loyalty and sales turnover. A study of the challenges of globalization on business strategies in modern organizations, with a case study of Amazon, was done on this basis.

Purpose of the Study

This study aimed at examining the challenges of globalization on business strategies in the Amazon U.S.

Specific Objectives

- To establish the relationship between financial globalization and business strategies in the Amazon;
- To set the relationship between technological globalization and business strategies of the Amazon;
- To assess the effect of financial globalization on the business strategies of Amazon; and
- To identify the different business strategies used by Amazon.

Research Questions

This research is focused on responding to the following questions:

1. What is the effect of economic globalization on the business strategies used in Amazon?
2. What relationship exists between technological globalization and business strategies used in Amazon?
3. What is the impact of financial globalization on business strategies used in Amazon?
4. What are the business strategies are used by Amazon?

Null Hypothesis

1. Economic globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in the Amazon.
2. There is no significant relationship between technological globalization and business strategies used in the Amazon.
3. Financial globalization does not have any significant effect on business strategies used in the Amazon.
4. Amazon does not use any business strategy in its business.

Importance of the Study

As a result of globalization, Amazon has grown from a simple online bookstore to several commercial disciplines. As a result, the study's conclusions are significant to Amazon's many shareowners, including shareholders, employees, sellers, and customers. Amazon shareholders can see the advantages and disadvantages and the challenges of globalization, which aid them in appreciating and identifying potential solutions, and so increasing the flow and financial performance of the company its new acquisitions and other like enterprises in general.

In addition to the scholarly literature, the study strives to unearth more practical information on the challenges of globalization. This research gives measurable inferences for future researchers to elaborate further on the relevance of globalization concerns to Internet enterprises and other modern organizations.

Definition of Terms

Business strategies: This study focused on identifying business owners' actions or decisions to reach business goals.

Challenges: This study defined challenges as problems/hindrances encountered while carrying out online transactions, including technological issues, which affect the company negatively.

E-commerce: This study set the parameters for what is known as e-commerce, which is selling and purchasing goods and services through the Internet.

Globalization: In this research, globalization was defined as exchanging people, companies, and governments between countries.

Limitations and Delimitations of the Study

The research focused on the problems of globalization in company strategy, with a particular focus on Amazon. This focal topic was picked because of Amazon's significance in globalization and its current position as a technology sector leader. For example, Amazon has grown from a bookstore to one of the world's largest tech companies, with its stock price surging from \$10 in 1994 to around \$3,000 today on the stock market, and its workforce has grown from 250 employees in Seattle to about 1,256,000 employees in nearly every country on the planet, with plans to move and explore life in space (Fildes & Perlet, 2020). Table 1 Shows the specific objectives and their corresponding research methodologies used in this study.

Table 1*Objectives and Method of Studying for Each Objective*

No.	Objective	Method
1.	To establish the relationship between Economic Globalization and business strategies in the Amazon	Quantitative
2.	To assess the relationship that exists between Technological Globalization and business strategies used in Amazon	Quantitative
3.	To assess the impact of Financial Globalization on the business strategies of Amazon	Mixed
4.	To identify the different business strategies used by Amazon	Qualitative

Chapter 2

Literature Review

The purpose of a literature review is to identify, locate, and analyze works that deal with the issue under investigation. Therefore, the literature on postharvest handling technology and revenue was reviewed in this chapter. It comprises the theories utilized and the study's core topics and interrelationships (Amin, 2005). In addition, secondary data about globalization collected through reputable research sources such as EBSCO host, ProQuest, SAGE, Jstor, and others were used.

Historical Review

Jeff Bezos, the company's current chairman and CEO, created Amazon.com, the world's largest electronic retailer, in 1994. A Princeton University alumnus with degrees in computer science and electrical engineering, Bezos created the corporation. Bezos relocated to Seattle following his retirement from D. E. Shaw, a Wall Street investment firm. Bezos had never used the Internet. However, he discovered that the Internet was growing at a rate of 2,300%, convincing him that this was a significant growth prospect. Bezos joined the world of e-commerce with no prior retail experience and scant knowledge. He chose Seattle as its headquarters because it possessed a massive pool of technical talent and was conveniently located near one of the largest book distributors in Roseburg, Oregon. Initially, he envisioned the business as a bookshop.

Additionally, Internet retailers are required to collect sales tax in the state in which they are incorporated. This suggests that the state's sales tax would increase the value of all transactions within the state at a competitive disadvantage (Krishnamurthy, 2006).

Amazon began as a small online bookstore, but it evolved into a giant online retail enterprise as a result of the Internet's rapid expansion toward the end of the 1990s. Amazon

currently accounts for one third of all Internet sales in the United States. The company's headquarters are in Seattle, and Amazon.com has developed sub websites dedicated to various countries, such as the United Kingdom (amazon.co.uk) and France (amazon.fr), since 1998. This expansion has resulted in the establishment of customer service centers, and 50,000 warehouses worldwide, which is a major change given that it began in a garage.

Amazon's goal is to become a one-stop shop for all online purchases; a one-stop shop grown from a small bookstore in Seattle to a \$48 billion retail behemoth. It was able to accomplish this as a result of technical innovation's strength. Through the years, computing data storage technologies has increased and become more affordable. Currently, Amazon sells products in more than 40 separate categories throughout the year. It stocks a variety of items, from literature to electronics to meals. In addition, Amazon is a logistics platform, a search engine, an Internet advertising platform, and an e-commerce and information technology platform. Amazon's primary goals are to provide customers with affordable prices, convenience, selection, and availability (Landrecht et al., 2018).

Initially, Bezos wished to construct a store that was devoid of traditional physical boundaries. It was not easy, but he did it, and by 2013, Amazon had 152 million customers and employed more than 70,000 employees worldwide. Furthermore, it generated a turnover of approximately \$61 billion in 2012, increasing 221% in less than 4 years. Along with Google, Apple, and Facebook, Amazon is one of the top four Internet companies. The corporation is exceptionally varied, selling a wide range of products, including digital content (e.g., movies), electrical equipment (e.g., laptops), and services such as Cloud Drive, Appstore, Cloud player, Amazon online services, and Amazon's best-seller: the Kindle.

In July 1995, the company debuted online. In May 1997, the company went public. Bezos and the early staff constructed desks out of doors and 4 X 4s to demonstrate the company's thriftiness. The business began in a garage. Ironically, the early business discussions occurred at a neighborhood Barnes and Noble. Cadabra was Bezos' first pick for a company name. He hastily changed his name after a lawyer he called mistakenly called it cadaver. He chose Amazon because it began with the letter A, conveyed a sense of significance, and was simple to spell. Bezos was named the 1999 *Time* Person of the Year for his accomplishments at 35, making him the magazine's fourth-youngest person of the year. "Bezos' vision of the internet retailing universe was so complete, his Amazon.com site so elegant and inviting, that it immediately established the de facto standard for everyone with anything to sell online," *Time* magazine explained in explaining why it chose Bezos (Krishnamurthy, 2006, p. 2).

The Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 depicts the independent variable, the dependent variable, and the moderating variable; in this case, globalization is the independent variable, with technological, economic, and sociocultural predictors; the dependent variable is marketing strategies, with the five P's serving as predictors, namely price, product, place, promotion, and people. Additionally, the conceptual framework depicts moderating elements such as government policies and political interactions.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework on Globalization and Business Strategies

The advancement of computing and communication technology has facilitated the movement of ideas and information across national borders, exposing customers worldwide. Because of the rapid flow of information, the Internet and networking have enabled smaller businesses to compete globally, independent of the seller’s or buyer’s physical location. Additionally, it allows multinational corporations to arrange business meetings with managers from headquarters and branches without wasting time on unnecessary travel.

Globalization has been defined as the world’s growing interconnectedness through cross-border flows of information, capital, and people (Held et al., 2002). While globalization affects economic, social, cultural, political, and other aspects of contemporary life, the researcher

focused on the economic, social-economic, and technological aspects, using the firm as the unit of analysis. Furthermore, since the study was investigating the challenges of globalization at the firm level, there was no attempt to measure the process of globalization directly but rather the degree to which companies are globalized in terms of the internationalization of their operations, revenues, and the competitive pressure they face. Taken together, these factors indicate the level of company globalization.

The objective is to understand better the relationship of globalization to e-commerce used by firms and its impacts on firm performance. E-commerce is broadly defined as the use of the Internet to buy, sell, or support products and services. The process of globalization is logically a powerful driver for firms to adopt specific Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) such as the Internet and e-commerce, as globalization usually has occurred earlier. There is also empirical evidence supporting the relationship. Macroeconomic evidence indicates that countries with more globally oriented economies (open in terms of trade and foreign investment) have higher levels of ICT investment (Kraemer et al., 2005).

Since it is affirming most of these investments, it is reasonable to expect that more globally oriented firms would be more likely to adopt technologies such as the Internet and e-commerce. Research has confirmed that this is the case (Caselli & Coleman, 2001). Other empirical studies at the country level support the argument that the opening markets trade and foreign investment lead domestic firms to invest in ICTs to remain competitive (Shih et al., 2005). Thus, the process of globalization is logically and empirically shown to be a driver for firms to adopt specific ICTs such as the Internet and e-commerce.

The framework posits that the degree to which a firm is already globalized will influence the extent to which it uses e-commerce and the types of e-commerce activities it undertakes. It

also posits that the degree of globalization will influence firm performance directly and indirectly by influencing the extent and nature of firm e-commerce activities, which also influences firm performance. The key variables in the framework are defined below in the methodology section. Next, a hypothesis was constructed from the relationships among these variables in the model, as represented by the arrows in Figure 1.

The Amazon Effect

The Amazon effect results from changes in customers' expectations, buying patterns, and industry competition as a result of the impact of the Internet, e-commerce, or digital marketplaces on the traditional brick-and-mortar business model. As Internet purchasing and e-commerce have risen in prominence, traditional businesses have had to contend with it by competing solely in the physical area. As of the early 1990s, Amazon.com Inc. developed an absolute stranglehold on the global online sales market, with the concept of the Amazon effect establishing itself as a household term. To date, studies on the effects of the Amazon effect have found that, among other things, it is responsible for the decline in brick-and-mortar retail sales, which have, in the past, forecast the end of these enterprises. Between 2008 and 2017, almost 9,400 retail locations closed, 53% more than the number that collapsed in the immediate aftermath of the Great Recession.

Changes in consumer shopping patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect. Additionally, today's shoppers anticipate a lot more variety even while visiting a physical retail location. For example, a retail store can see the product specifics of electrical devices and cashews, but it is not feasible to see the information on the products on major online purchasing sites. Today's shopper expects smoothness, timeliness, and convenience, even with services (such as at a salon). When customers go online, they can read customer comments on the product

instantaneously and see how they feel about it. Increased production, technological advancements, transit speed, and communication have contributed to increased capital, labor, information, and technology transfer. As a result, economies worldwide are increasingly interdependent and entwined (Savrul et al., 2014).

The growth in the popularity of online shopping has accelerated significantly in recent years. One significant benefit of e-commerce is that there are no geographic constraints, and customers may access a wide range of goods from any location or time they choose.

Additionally, clients have a wide variety of items from which to choose. With these advantages, shoppers transfer their buying habits from brick-and-mortar retail locations to online purchasing.

A survey of Internet shoppers found that 48% had shopped online in the preceding year, 66% favored online shops, and 73% had done nearly half of their buying online. Thus, online shopping is growing in popularity, and with that growth, Amazon can use its fundamental capabilities. How to lead? To serve and inspire (Landrecht et al., 2018).

Summary of Past Research

Globalization and Management in Amazon

Amazon is an Internet company. Barcode and IT surveillance are two powerful instruments of management in Amazon. IT systems allow managers to follow up on all items and employees. Everyone is under surveillance. Their productivity can be seen in real time. The pressure is extreme on the logistics employees and the managers who must fulfill all their tasks. According to an article (Garnett, 2019), Amazon has also managed to integrate a new gadget into robots to detect when someone is approaching slow down to void an incident, safeguarding workplace health and safety. In addition, robots assist them in doing tasks more efficiently and effectively and contribute to a company's success and growth (Meyer, 2017).

All Amazon's sites are created and managed simultaneously in terms of globalization, no matter the location. Furthermore, Amazon's management should be called "control management." Their strong management policies encourage the tracking and denouncement of other employees. A French journalist worked undercover for Amazon during Christmastime of 2012 and described the pressure and the tracking of the employees in a book. With technology-powered shopping portals, clients may do average monthly grocery orders more quickly than with traditional websites. In addition, customized offers and promotions delivered to customers while shopping portals benefit the site because they have a high possibility of being purchased. For traditional shops, these functionalities are not available, and they are expensive. Because real estate is so costly, retailers are disadvantaged because they cannot rent shop space cheaply.

The economic life of this company has been made possible because Amazon has made many advances in its use of technology. Its use of technology has played a vital role in the globalization of the company. There have been many technological opportunities that are offered to consumers, investors, and businesses. Amazon has the chance to set a fast and informed trend in its company. This allows it to have a quicker transfer of its investor's assets and collaborate with their partners (Bezos et al., 2021).

Other empirical studies at the country level support the argument that Amazon was opening markets to trade, and foreign investment leads domestic firms to invest in ICTs to remain competitive (Bezos et al., 2021). The process of globalization is logically and empirically shown to be a driver for firms to adopt specific ICTs such as the Internet and e-commerce.

Globalization and Marketing Strategies in Amazon

The process of globalization is logically a powerful driver for firms to adopt specific ICTs such as the Internet and e-commerce, as it usually has occurred earlier. There is also

empirical evidence supporting the relationship. Macroeconomic evidence indicates that countries with more globally oriented economies (open in terms of trade and foreign investment) have higher levels of ICT investment (Incekara & Savrul, 2017).

Since firms are making the most of these investments, it is reasonable to expect that more globally oriented firms would be more likely to adopt the Internet and e-commerce. Research has confirmed that this is the case (Shih et al., 2005).

Amazon continues to grow and improve as a world-class e-commerce platform by delivering more of what customers want: low prices, a broad selection, and convenience. “Things arrive on your doorstep in two days when you order from Amazon, but consumers do not think about how,” said George Prest in an interview (Donald, 2019), CEO of a logistics trade association. According to Danziger (2020) of *Forbes* magazine Amazon used a risky approach to the business strategy that paid off handsomely. This goal remains the sellers, developers, content creators, consumers, and businesses. Amazon has always attempted to meet the needs of each of these groups by inventing innovative solutions that make things a little faster, better, easier, and most cost-effective (Bezos et al., 2021).

The introduction of Amazon Go, a new store with no need to check out, is the most recent illustration of its business plan innovation. Users of the Amazon Go app enter the store, grab what they want, and leave without having to queue or check out, resulting in a “Just Walk Out Shopping experience” (Bezos et al., 2021, p. 5). Amazon has also just released a smartphone app for its Kindle services, allowing customers to access instantly the online sales platform and check items before purchasing. In the future, the use of 3D virtual technologies to advertise products will propel Internet shopping to new heights (Landrecht et al., 2018).

Amazon's success has relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases. Many dot-coms collapsed as a result of a lack of belief rather than awareness. Amazon underlines how it plans to accomplish this in its SEC filing. This consumer focus has translated into service excellence, with Amazon.com receiving an 88, the highest customer satisfaction score ever recorded in any service business, according to the 2004 American Customer Satisfaction Index (Cook & Ross, 2004). In March 1999, Amazon auctions (also known as z Shops) were launched, primarily as a result of eBay's popularity. The main website, category pages, and specific product pages all gave it much attention. Despite this, it only had a 3.2% share of the online auction market a year after its launch, compared to eBay's 58%, and it has only plummeted since then (Bezos et al., 2021).

Third-party merchants in Amazon Marketplaces, which are into traditional product listings, provide competitive product prices. Amazon's marketing strategy for marketplaces included creating such an auction service, which was first needed to compete with eBay. However, the technique has been updated, and Amazon refers to it as part of the low-cost strategy. This is in line with the advice of Chaffey (2021), who suggested that lessons be learned from Amazon's digital marketing approach because it employs it effectively across all customer communications touchpoints in Amazon's RACE Framework:

Reach: Amazon's first commercial growth is based on a thorough SEO and AdWords strategy that targeted millions of keywords.

Act: Using testing and learning, create clear and straightforward experiences.

Convert: Using customization to make relevant recommendations and a simple checkout procedure, many businesses are copying.

Engage: Customers are delighted by Amazon's customer-centric culture, which keeps them coming back for more.

Amazon has established its internal experimentation platform, dubbed a Web lab, which it uses to test new features and functionality for Amazon's websites and products. In 2013, the company operated 1,976 Web labs globally, up from 1,092 during 2012 and 546 in the previous year, 2011. Although many firms employ A/B testing, this example highlights the breadth of Amazon's testing. As Amazon's stock price increased, it created opportunities for collaborations and acquisitions with a range of different businesses. Amazon was able to show how it partnered with Living.com (furniture), Wineshopper.com (an online wine store), Drugstore.com (an e-pharmacy), Pets.com (a pet supplies store), HomeGrocer.com (for home groceries), Sothebys.com (an auction site), and Kozmo.com (also an online auction site). In the majority of situations, Amazon acquired an ownership stake in these businesses to benefit from their success. Additionally, it charged them for promoting and generating traffic to their websites via Amazon placements (Bezos et al., 2021).

Similarly, Amazon's business strategy was to charge authors for prime-position advertising on its site, which sparked outrage at first but subsided when it was discovered that paying for prominent placements was common in traditional bookshops and supermarkets. Many of these new online businesses collapsed in 1999 and 2000, but Amazon had covered the potential for development and was not dragged down by these partners, even though it had invested 50% in some, such as Pets.com (Bezos et al., 2021).

Amazon Go is a unique shopping place. Consumers must access the store using the Amazon Go app, but there are no lineups and no checkout once inside. Instead, consumers can select the things they desire from the shelf, and Amazon will bill the customer's Amazon account

upon exiting the store. Amazon Marketing Service was the company's initial product advertising platform. It was then phased out and replaced with Amazon Advertising. This new gateway provides Sellers with a streamlined method for managing their media, marketing, and advertising under a single unified umbrella (Bezos et al., 2021).

Amazon's affiliate program has connected Amazon with other smaller enterprises because of the profitability it provides to them. Amazon has maintained the Associate's Program since it was first created in July 1996, and it is still alive and well today (Bezos et al., 2021).

Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work. So, if Amazon is betting money to produce a product or service, then it will not be frightened to fail even if Amazon had a chance of failure (Bezos et al., 2021).

Amazon's logistics system is far superior to that of other worldwide retailers, and it is one of the key ways the company fulfills its goal of being the most customer-centric company in the world. As a result, Amazon invests substantially in its logistical infrastructure, from distribution centers near key cities to a cutting-edge robot system. Despite its scale, Amazon's agility allows it to stay ahead of its competitors. This is because the organization contains several built-in processes that ensure team flexibility and decision-making speed. For example, a two-pizza rule is a well-known approach for keeping problem-solving groups small and forcing decision making. In addition, Amazon is a one-stop shop when it comes to fragmentation. It is a media firm that produces high-quality television and film programming, a cloud-based web service, and an online store (Banker, 2021).

Globalization and Costing Strategies in Amazon

Amazon has set a series of ambitious goals, which is shown by its incredible vision. It has a mission to provide clients with the lowest possible costs, the best available choices, and the utmost

persuasion. This mission statement offers both customers and the company a promise of satisfaction. Amazon's overall success may be summarized into three fundamental factors: lowest costs, a broad assortment of products, and providing customers with the most incredible ease (Gregory, 2019).

Stone (2018) mentioned that Amazon's current mission is to make customers feel comfortable browsing online and find just about anything they would want. From a garage-based bookseller to a 48-billion-dollar retail machine, Amazon has transformed. Thanks to the progress of technology, they have been able to do this. Although computational power, bandwidth, and data storage technologies have increased and become less expensive, these technologies have all reached a greater capacity over time.

Consumers can quickly request price-matching across distribution channels and locations by using computers and mobile phones. Arbitrage is possible even if location-specific pricing discrepancies exist. Thus, retailers should match prices. Amazon provides products in more than different categories in the present day. Customers can get books, electronics, groceries, and more at this location. Amazon has found several new e-commerce and online marketing positions, including a logistics provider, search engine, Internet advertising platform, and e-commerce platform. For Amazon, the main priorities are cheap pricing, convenience, and a wide range of options (Chaffey, 2021).

Amazon's price approach keeps customers coming back for more. Amazon is a one-stop shop for any number of products customers could be in the market for, including fashion, toiletries, and gadgets. They are clicking the "Buy" button to purchase an item at a discounted price. So, it is essential to remember that members of the Prime loyalty program get free shipping on qualifying purchases as quickly as overnight. Amazon's price strategy is drastically different from

competitors, as it wages battle in businesses that are rendered uncompetitive by other competitors.

When shopping on Amazon, the probability of purchasing identical goods is higher, and the average price difference between locations is lower. The findings agree with earlier research conducted by Ater and Rigbi (2017), which concluded that Internet visibility has a limiting effect on brick-and-mortar stores' capacity to implement a pricing discrimination strategy across different locations.

Challenges of Globalization in Amazon

Manshady and Totonchi (2012) posited that firms use the Internet and electronic trade as a gateway to globalization. In order to compete on an equal playing field with global competitors, local enterprises will need to expand their foreign business. The increased integration of the world economy raises several new problems for multinational firms in capital investment and leadership. It is critical to set up a business in a new country, especially a developing one, because of the required capital that is required to do so. Even if the infrastructure is in place, it may not be required. This is corroborated by the evidence (Kaushal & Jain, 2017). Setting up a website and providing items or services to the world does not suffice to conduct business across national borders. To make it possible for corporations to do business on the Internet, companies will need to establish virtual, financial, and information procedures that global enterprises already have in place but are much more complex and expensive for local firms to imitate.

Amazon utilizes a tremendous amount of data storage. Accordingly, Elastic Block Store, an Amazon product, has had seven electric outages since the year began. This issue is mainly caused by Amazon's largest and oldest data center in Virginia, generating data center outages.

To prevent a service outage in the future, the corporation will have to make extensive changes to the U.S. East data center. In addition, if the server crashes, customers might suffer.

Amazon makes long-term investments because its primary goal is to reap the advantages of those investments later. Amazon has slowed in recent years, but its margin has remained consistent. Previous studies have shown, “Firms must increase its margins to maintain the stock price” (Nanda & Narayandas, 2021, p. 98). Based on the variety of obstacles faced by e-commerce in India, Tikendrajit and Ningombam (1970) concentrated on understanding the growth potential of e-commerce in India. Additionally, retailers should stay in touch with customers via e-commerce. Before implementing e-commerce strategies, it is vital to consider many critical variables, including customer convenience, multichannel investments, and uniqueness or transparency.

Manshady and Totonchi (2012) showed that firms only think about globalization in adopting specific ICTs, such as the Internet and e-commerce. In order to compete on an equal playing field with global competitors, local enterprises will need to expand their foreign business. Setting up a website and providing items or services to the world does not suffice to conduct business across national borders. To make it possible for corporations to do business on the Internet, companies will need to establish virtual, financial, and information procedures that global enterprises already have in place but are much more complex and expensive for local firms to imitate.

The process of globalization creates new challenges and opportunities for firms. The opportunities include access to new markets that were previously closed because of cost, regulation, or indirect barriers; the ability to tap resources such as labor, capital, and knowledge on a worldwide basis; and the opportunity to participate in global production networks that are

becoming prevalent in many industries such as automotive, electronics, toys, and textile. On the other hand, challenges come from foreign competitors entering firm' domestic markets, and from domestic competitors reducing their costs through global sourcing, moving production offshore, or gaining economies of scale by expanding into new markets (Giovanni et al., 2008).

Globalization challenges firms to become more streamlined and efficient while simultaneously extending the geographic reach of their operations. Responding to these opportunities and challenges increasingly requires a fundamental restructuring of organizational strategy and processes. Because of increased competitive pressure, companies use new technologies to extend their products and operations into the international marketplace. They are also using these technologies to achieve new innovative transnational organizational forms (Sturgeon, 2002).

According to Gupta and Batra (2016), e-commerce provides multiple benefits to customers in terms of lower cost and more variety and saves time. The buying can be done with a click of a mouse without going anywhere. Various services, including online banking, ticket booking, and payment of bills, have provided several significant benefits to consumers. As a result, it has emerged as a boundary-less trade medium. E-commerce works on four functions.

- Communication: Related to providing information/ documents for business transactions.
- Process Management: Automation and improvements in business processes;
- Service Management: Technology to improve service quality; and
- Transaction Capabilities: The ability to buy/sell on the Internet or other online options.

According to Chai (2020), e-commerce can be categorized as:

- Business to Business: A marketplace for businesses to sell their products and services to other businesses (i.e., retailers or corporate consumers). For example, Alibaba.
- Business to Consumers: Selling of products and services to consumers. For example, Amazon, eBay, Rediff, yahoo.
- Customer to Customer): A marketplace for consumers to sell products and services through a business organization that acts as a facilitator (e.g., olx, naukri.com, monster.com.) Apart from the categories mentioned above, there are other lesser-known ones: Government-to-Consumer, Government-to-Business, Consumer-to-Business, Consumer-to-Government, Business-to-Government, and Government-to-Government.

The adoption and use of ICTs such as the Internet make it cheaper and more accessible for firms to extend their markets, manage their operations, and coordinate value chains across borders (Globerman & Shapiro, 2002; Zou & Cavusgil, 2002). As Greenspan (2001) said, “By lowering the costs of transactions and information, technology has reduced market frictions and provided significant impetus to the process of broadening world markets” (p. 1). ICT use fosters globalization by reducing transaction and coordination costs and creating new and expanded markets with economies of scale (Greenspan, 2001).

Much of the literature on globalization and IT lacks empirical analysis but implicitly treats globalization as the dependent variable and examines the impacts of IT and the Internet. While there is acknowledge that there is a reciprocal relationship between the two and do not make absolute claims of causality, Amazon reversed the typical hypothesized ordering of effects. Instead, it suggests that globalization occurs first, creating conditions for firms to adopt and use

e-commerce for improved performance. It is imperative to examine the challenges of globalization and a firm's business strategies because the process of globalization has preceded Internet and e-commerce adoption in time, and it is still too early to observe common effects (Kraemer et al., 2005).

Globalization and Firm Performance

The previous studies anticipated a direct relationship between globalization and firm performance and hope that highly global firms perform efficiently, with better coordination of trading partners, and improved market position. It is likely that globalization internationally realizes more significant impacts on performance because firms can now employ resources and capabilities developed throughout their global operations to improve business processes and more effectively deploy technologies such as e-commerce (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 1991).

International firms are also better positioned to benefit from e-commerce to achieve economies of scale and global reach (Porter, 1986). Finally, firms with a more significant global scope are likely to face more substantial transaction costs as a result of their expansion into diverse geographic regions, and e-commerce use may help reduce such transaction costs (Garicano & Kaplan, 2001; Malone et al., 1987). A firm's global scope is a significant predictor of e-commerce value in the financial services industry (Zhu & Kraemer, 2005). Globalization should also indirectly affect performance through e-commerce use since highly global firms will use e-commerce extensively, resulting in improved performance. E-commerce use will mediate the challenges of globalization on firm performance.

Summary

Chapter 2 focused on reviewing related literature and looked at the study variables, including technology, economic factors, social, cultural factors, inflation, government policies

and political relations, and study objectives. The purpose of this chapter for the study was to identify research gaps, appreciate the previous writers, and use the data as a basis for the generation of primary data for the current study.

Indeed, most of the literature talks about the different variables, including technology, economic factors, social, cultural factors, inflation, government policies, and political relations, but it also explains their effects on business strategies. However, the general meanings and implications in the findings and conclusions of the different researchers apply and help understand aspects of globalization.

Lead to Chapter 3

The literature review served as the base for Chapter 3, which shows the methodology and procedures used in the study and the technical ways with which the study was conducted.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter gives a preamble to the adapted methodology; it describes the methodology concerning the challenges of globalization on business strategies in modern organizations in a case study of the Amazon. Then, the chapter covers the study research design, the target population area of study, sample technique and sample design, data collection, procedure, instruments, data analysis, presentation methods, research design, the study area, the target population, the sampling procedure, data collection methods, and data management. Finally, the scope and limitations of the study are examined in this chapter.

Research Design

This study was descriptive and cross-sectional in design. While cross-sectional designs are suitable for studies done at one point in time, descriptive studies seek to find what is happening concerning a particular phenomenon, why it is happening, and how it is happening. The study used a descriptive design to obtain information about the challenges of globalization on business strategies in modern organizations, focusing on Amazon. This described what exists concerning variables or conditions in globalization and how they affected business strategies.

The study described the challenges of globalization on business strategies. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were used to generate information because neither is indispensable to the other, according to Dey (1993). Therefore, quantitative methods were used to capture quantifiable information. In contrast, qualitative methods were used to collect qualitative information that is difficult to quantify, which allowed the elicitation of voices of critical informants from whom the information was obtained (Amin, 2005).

This research design is the most suitable because it enabled the researcher to understand the topic better. It is also less expensive and more time saving than the quantitative experiments; it allowed for the collection of large amounts of data for an in-depth study on the challenges of globalization on business strategies in the modern organization. Because descriptive design is used to describe and not make any conclusions, it is essential in helping the researcher show the challenges of globalization on business strategies. Data collection methods such as the interview method, questionnaire, observation methods, and content analysis are discussed in detail regarding how they are used and the extent of their effectiveness.

Restatement of the Research Objectives

- To find out the effect of economic globalization on the Business strategies used in Amazon;
- To assess the relationship that exists between Technological globalization and business strategies used in Amazon;
- To investigate the effect of financial globalization on business strategies used in Amazon; and
- To find out what business strategies Amazon uses.

Survey Instrument

Questionnaire

According to Sekaran (2003) and Creswell (2010), a questionnaire makes collecting quantitative data easier. A questionnaire is a technique for collecting information, opinions, perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs from many people at one time. Close-ended questionnaires were used to facilitate the quantitative data collection (Appendix A). Close-ended questionnaires are objective instruments since the prescribed questions and responses free them from the

interviewer and interviewee's opinions and biases. The questionnaire was sent to 111 employees who were chosen at random to complete it. The questionnaire was chosen to collect this type of data because it is a quick and easy way to collect information, especially when the researcher understands precisely what they need and how to quantify the variables of interest. It also enables the researcher to collect a large amount of data in a short period.

The respondents were assured that their information was confidential since they did not need to indicate their names anywhere on the questionnaire. The framing and phrasing of the questions allowed the respondents to answer quickly without assistance since they were set in elementary language. The questionnaires were administered directly or within the participating distance of the principal researcher, who explained the background, aims, objectives of the problem under investigation, and the necessity of giving correct answers (See Appendix A).

A Key Informant Interview Guide

To obtain information from the key informants, a critical informant interview guide was employed. Managers in various Amazon companies will benefit the most from this. This is something that gives the knowledge to help with the interview. It is a list of questions or subjects that will be explored throughout the interview.

Documentary Review Checklist

A documentary review checklist was used for carrying out the documentary review. This is an instrument that contains a list of all documents to be reviewed.

Validity of the Instrument

Validity is the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of data represent the phenomenon under study. This is the ability of the instrument to collect truthful and justifiable data (Oso & Onen, 2009). The validity of the instrument will be determined by using the content

validity method. The researcher will construct questionnaires and submit them to the supervisor, who will examine and approve them for their validity. Instruments were also pilot tested, after which the Content Validity Index will be computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Content Validity Index} = \frac{\text{Number of Valid Items}}{\text{Total number of items}} \times 100$$

It was found out that the Content Validity Index = 89.8%

The research tools were considered valid since the Content Validity Index was 89.8%, above 0.6, the commendable Content Validity Index as amended by Mugenda and Mugenda (2003). Furthermore, the instruments were found to have content validity because they covered all the possible aspects of the research topic.

Reliability of the Instrument

On the other hand, reliability measures the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials (Sekaran, 2003). To determine the reliability of the research instruments, a pretest was undertaken in a similar environment using the same tools, the instruments were pretested with 10 respondents, and Cronbach's alpha was used to correlate to the score of the responses.

Reliability tests were carried out to measure the accuracy of the instruments used to collect data. The consistency of the items was calculated using Cronbach formula:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \times \left(1 - \frac{\sum SD_{2i}^2}{SD_{2t}^2} \right)$$

Where α = Alpha Coefficient of correlation
 K = number of scores in instruments
 SD_{2i} = Variance of scores on individual

$$SD2t = \text{Variance out on the total test}$$
$$\sum = \text{Sum of}$$

Alpha was found above 0.5 ($\alpha = 0.68$), confirming a substantially high correlation coefficient, and therefore, the questionnaires were used with sufficient reliability.

Data Collection

An introductory letter was presented to relevant units in Amazon and respondents to authenticate the research activities. In this visit, the researcher intended to explain to the Amazon leadership the steps taken and how to conduct the study. This study relied on two complementary sources of data: primary and secondary. First, the study embraced a comprehensive survey of the literature on globalization and how it affects business strategies. Based on this secondary research, the researcher intended to synthesize numerous globalization factors and how they affect business strategies and draw parallels between findings in modern organizations and bias toward Amazon. The researcher intended to derive a discussion on the challenges of globalization on business strategies. The secondary sources of this study were obtained through an in-depth analysis of relevant data that offer the problem's background. Secondary evidence included books, journal articles, government reports, articles, seminars papers, and so forth.

The primary data were collected from the target population through questionnaires. The questionnaires were structured, and semi structured self-administering questionnaires were designed to capture both the qualitative and quantitative data relating to the challenges of globalization on business strategies in the modern organization.

The unstructured interview was administered in a face-to-face setting with respondents left free to express their views and at the same time concern taken to ensure that critical information is not left out. To gather the ideas and voices of Amazon employees, an Internet

survey was used via the surveymonkey.com platform. To gain access to Amazon personnel, the researcher got a letter of acceptance from the company's managers. However, face-to-face interviews were not possible; therefore, the researcher utilized tools such as Zoom and Amazon Chime to achieve the same.

However, it is essential to note that the study did not claim to provide an exhaustive review of all challenges of globalization, but it is aimed at key challenges of globalization on business strategies in a modern organization, in a case of Amazon.

Data Analysis

The process of providing order, structure, and meaning to a large amount of data to extract useable and valuable information is known as data analysis. The following methods of analysis were used to analyze both quantitative and qualitative data.

Quantitative Data Analysis

In this study, descriptive analysis was used in analyzing the data because the study analyzed the variables. The primary data integrated facts and assumptions obtained directly from the fieldwork through interviews, and structured questionnaires were sorted and edited to eliminate errors to ensure completeness, accuracy, and uniformity. Coding was done after editing to reduce data from detailed to summarized and understand the data. After coding, data entry and stat cleaning was done. Then, using SPSS software, descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency distributions, and cross-tabulations were used to analyze the data. The data generated were further subjected to a Pearson correlation test analysis and a regression analysis since these tests were best suited for determining the cause-effect relationship of the variable. Finally, the information from the above process was presented in frequency tables, charts, figures, and diagrams.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data obtained by using key informant interviews and documentary reviews were sorted, edited, and arranged according to themes category by category, based on the study objectives. Content analysis was done according to the themes and interpretations made and reported.

Measurement of Variables

The study used the nominal and ordinal scales in measuring variables, especially in the quantitative analysis. For example, the nominal scales were used to rate characteristics such as gender, position type, and specialty, while the ordinal scale was used to rate the responses from the Likert statements to show the level of agreement or disagreement (Sekaran, 2003).

Population

The population included senior- and middle-level managers and other selected staff from different operating units of the Amazon Web Services (Administration, Strategy, Advertising, IMDB, Music, Corporate development), Worldwide consumer (Fulfilment, Physical stores, OSHA, Global Delivery, Wholefoods markets, Amazon Prime, and Fresh), Amazon Devices and Digital Management (lab 126, Ring, Blink, Alexa), Amazon Videos and studios (Prime videos, Sports Video, Video On-Demand). The study was held at Amazon offices and remotely through video conferencing tools such as Zoom and Skype. In addition, the researcher analyzed issues of globalization and its challenges to business strategies. Globally, Amazon has more than 1.2 million employees, with about 20,000 in Massachusetts. With the above background information, a total target population of 150 employees of Amazon was selected at random from Amazon Web Services, Worldwide consumer, Amazon Devices and Digital Management, Amazon Videos and studios, and Amazon robotics (Fildes & Perlet, 2020).

Sampling Techniques

Table 2 served as a guide for the sampling technique. From the target population of 150 people, 111 were selected as the sample selected from the Amazon corporation's five key divisions or business units. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling approaches were used in the investigation. Each item in the population had an equal probability of being included in the sample under simple random sampling (Kothari, 2004).

Table 2

Sampling Procedure

S/N	Category	Target Population	Sample	Sampling Procedure
1	Amazon Web Services (Administration, Strategy, Advertising, IMDB, Music, Corporate development)	30	21	Random and Purposive sampling
2	Worldwide consumer (Fulfilment, Physical stores, GO, Books First, Fresh, Global Delivery-Prime AIR, Electric Vehicles, Wholefoods markets, Amazon Prime, and Fresh)	30	24	Random and Purposive sampling
3	Amazon Devices and Digital Management (lab 126, Ring, Blink, Alexa)	30	24	Random and Purposive sampling
4	Amazon Videos and studios (Prime videos, Sports Video, Video On-Demand)	30	23	Random and Purposive sampling

(continued)

S/N	Category	Target Population	Sample	Sampling Procedure
5	Robotics and Project Kuiper	30	19	Random and Purposive sampling
	Grand Total	150	111	

To pick respondents in Amazon's divisions or business units, simple random and purposive sampling were employed. Purposive sampling is the deliberate selection of specific population units for research, resulting in a sample representing the population (Kothari, 2004). Key leaders and managers were chosen using purposive sampling since they were expected to know about the phenomenon under inquiry. The questionnaires were distributed to 111 employees, who were chosen at random to fill them out; the questionnaire was sent out electronically via [surveymonkey.com](https://www.surveymonkey.com).

Chapter 4

Presentation and Analysis of Findings

This chapter focused on data presentation and analysis of findings and is illustrated below.

Level of Education

This study learned about respondents' levels of education to determine respondents' capacity to read and write, which also reflected that the respondents clearly understood what was asked and could answer by their levels of perception about the study objectives. Table 3 shows respondent's level of education, and 29 (26.1%) were diploma holders, 19 (17.1%) had B.A. Degree, 13 (11.7%) were B.A. Postgraduates, 12 (10.8%) had certificate, 12 (10.8%) had B.Sc. Degree, 11 (9.9%) were B.Sc. Postgraduates, 11 (9.9%) had a master's degree, and only 4 (3.6%) had a Ph.D. This means majority of respondents approached in this study were diploma holders.

Table 3

Respondent's Level of Education

	Frequency	Percent
Certificate	12	10.8
Diploma Holder	29	26.1
B.A. Degree	19	17.1
B.Sc. Degree	12	10.8
Valid B.A. Postgraduate	13	11.7
B.Sc. Postgraduate	11	9.9
Master's Degree	11	9.9
Ph.D.	4	3.6
Total	111	100.0

Figure 2 shows respondents' level of education, and 26.1% of the respondents were diploma holders, 17.1% had a B.A. degree, 11.7% had a certificate, 10.8% had a BSc degree, 9.9% had a postgraduate, and 9.9% had a master's degree. This means the majority of the respondents in this study were qualified with a certificate; hence, an implication that they could tell what the study was all about and understand the different variables used in the study.

Figure 2

Education Level of the Respondents

Gender

This study asked about the gender of the respondents to determine the level of gender balance Amazon exhibited and to prove this study considered gender sensitivity during data collection.

Data in Table 4 indicate results on the gender of the respondents, and 53(57.7%) were male, 41(36.9%) were female, and 17(15.3%) were the third gender. This means that majority of the respondents approached in this study were males. This is an indicator of gender sensitivity

since at least every gender is reflected with respondents despite the majority being males; hence this can reflect economic globalization-related challenges on the set business strategy.

Table 4

Showing Gender of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Male	53	47.7
Female	41	36.9
Third gender	17	15.3
Total	111	100.0

Figure 3 shows that 47.7% of the respondents were male, 36.9% female, and 15.3% transgender. This means that most of the respondents approached in this study were male; however, there was a significant other gender, which is an indication that Amazon welcomes and employs all kinds of people.

Figure 3

Gender of the Respondents

Status of Respondent’s Appointment

This study asked about the status of the respondent’s appointment to determine the level of worker commitment toward enabling Amazon to achieve the set business strategy and whether this posed a challenge toward achieving the set business strategy.

Data in Table 5 shows results on the status of respondent’s appointment, and 32 (28.8%) indicated part-time, 29 (26.1%) indicated subsidiaries, 27 (24.3%) indicated full-time, and 23 (20.7%) indicated contractors. This means that most of the respondents indicated part-time as the status of their appointment, an indicator of the possibility of low commitment, hence, reflecting financial globalization-related challenges that affect business strategy.

Table 5

Showing Status of Respondent’s Appointment

	Frequency	Percent
Part-time	32	28.8
Full time	27	24.3
Valid Contractors	23	20.7
Subsidiaries	29	26.1
Total	111	100.0

Distribution of Respondents Among the Five Key Business Units of Amazon Corporations

This study asked about the distribution of respondents among the five key business units of Amazon Corporations with the aim of the business unit with the majority of its workers and to determine whether this business unit had more challenges to the set strategy.

Table 6 shows results on the distribution of respondents among the five key business units of Amazon Corporations and 28 (25.2%) indicated Amazon devices and Digital

Management, 23 (20.7%) indicated Worldwide consumer, 22 (19.8%) indicated Amazon Web Services, 21 (18.9%) indicated Amazon Videos and studios, and finally 17 (15.3%) indicated Robotics and project Kuiper. This means that majority of the respondents indicated that they belonged to Amazon devices and digital management. This indicates there are higher numbers of employees in Amazon devices and digital management than other business units. The products and services in this unit reflect the possibility of economic, technical, and financial globalization-related challenges on the set business strategy.

Table 6

Showing Results on the Distribution of Respondents Among the Five Key Business Units of Amazon Corporations

	Frequency	Percent
Amazon Web Services	22	19.8
Worldwide consumer	23	20.7
Amazon Devices and Digital	28	25.2
Valid Management		
Amazon Videos and studios	21	18.9
Robotics and Project Kuiper	17	15.3
Total	111	100.0

Objective 1: To Establish the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon

To establish the relationship between economic globalization and business strategies in Amazon, this study attempted to ask a few questions from which answers concluded whether economic globalization had a positive or a significant negative relationship with business

strategy in Amazon. Table 7 illustrates results on the relationship between economic globalization and business strategies in Amazon.

Table 7

Results on the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon

Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Economic Globalization directly promotes growth in Amazon.	F %	15 13.5	25 22.5	3 2.7	49 44.1	19 17.1
Globalization has increased job opportunities in Amazon.	F %	16 14.4	32 28.8	3 2.7	44 39.6	16 14.4
Workers are using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents.	F %	22 19.8	26 23.4	4 3.6	42 37.8	17 15.3
Through globalization, Amazon can manage its international operations in more efficient ways.	F %	19 17.1	23 20.7	2 1.8	47 42.3	20 18
Amazon has been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist.	F %	29 26.1	18 16.2	2 1.8	38 34.2	24 21.6
Amazon has a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team.	F %	25 22.5	19 17.1	10 9	46 41.4	11 9.9

(continued)

Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Amazon has created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customer's wallets.	F	24	25	3	39	20
	%	21.6	22.5	2.7	35.1	18
Shoppers had to travel to stores to discover goods and buy things before Amazon.	F	26	23	4	34	24
	%	23.4	20.7	3.6	30.6	21.6

Economic Globalization Directly Promotes Growth in Amazon

The results in Table 7 show that 49 (44.1%) agreed and 19 (17.1%) strongly agreed, totaling of 66 (61.2%), to the statement that economic globalization directly promotes growth in Amazon. However, 25 (22.5%) disagreed, as well as 15 (13.5%) strongly disagreed align to 40 (36%), implying that economic globalization indirectly promotes growth in Amazon. Therefore, 3 (2.7%) of the respondents were undecided on whether economic globalization directly promotes growth in Amazon. This means that majority of the respondents indicated that economic globalization directly promotes growth in Amazon.

Globalization Has Increased Job Opportunities in Amazon

The results in Table 7 show that 44 (39.6%) agreed and 16 (14.4%) strongly agreed, totaling 60 (54%), to the statement that globalization has increased job opportunities in Amazon. However, 32 (28.8%) disagreed, as well as 16 (14.4%) strongly disagreed, totaling 48 (43.3%), implying that globalization has decreased job opportunities in Amazon. Therefore, 3 (2.7%) of the respondents were undecided on whether globalization has increased job opportunities in

Amazon. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that globalization has increased job opportunities in Amazon.

Workers Are Using Digital Platforms to Learn, Find Work, and Showcase Their Talents

Data in Table 7 show that 42 (37.8%) agreed and 17 (15.3%) strongly agreed, totaling 59 (53.1%), to the statement that workers are using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents. However, 26 (23.4%) disagreed, as well as 22 (19.8%) strongly disagreed, totaling 48(43.2%), implying that workers are not using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents. Therefore, 4 (3.6%) of the respondents were undecided on whether workers use digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that workers are using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents, thus, improving the productivity of Amazon.

Through Globalization, Amazon Can Manage Its International Operations in More Efficient Ways

The results in Table 7 show that 47 (42.3%) agreed and 20 (18%) strongly agreed, totaling 67 (60.3%), to the statement that through globalization, Amazon can manage its international operations in more efficient ways. However, 23 (20.7%) disagreed, as well as 19 (17.1%) strongly disagreed, totaling 42 (37.8%), implying that through globalization, Amazon cannot manage its international operations in more efficient ways. Therefore, 2 (1.8%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon can manage its international operations more efficiently through globalization. This means that most respondents indicated that Amazon could manage its international operations more efficiently through globalization.

Amazon Has Been Recognized as One of the Most Successful Companies to Exist

The results in Table 7 show that 38 (34.2%) agreed and 24 (21.6%) strongly agreed, totaling 62 (55.8%), to the statement that Amazon has been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist. However, 29 (26.1%) disagreed, as well as 18 (16.2%) strongly disagreed, totaling 47 (42.3%), implying that Amazon has not been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist. Of the respondents, 2 (1.8%) were undecided on whether Amazon has been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon had been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist.

Amazon Has a Raft of Procedures to Guide Its Disparate Team

The results in Table 7 show that 46 (41.4%) agreed and 11 (9.9%) strongly agreed, totaling 57(51.3%), to the statement that Amazon has a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team. However, 19 (17.1%) disagreed, as well as 25 (22.5%) strongly disagreed, totaling 44 (39.6%), implying that Amazon does not have a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team. Of the respondents, 10 (9%) were undecided on whether Amazon has a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon has a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team.

Amazon Has Created Economic Ripple Effects That Go Beyond the Customers' Wallets

The results in Table 7 show that 39 (35.1%) agreed and 20 (18%) strongly agreed, totaling 59 (53.1%), to the statement that Amazon has created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customers' wallets. However, 25 (22.5%) disagreed, as well as 24 (21.6%) strongly disagreed, totaling 49 (44.1%), implying that Amazon has not created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customer's wallets. Of the respondents, 3 (2.7%) were undecided on whether

Amazon has created economic ripple effects beyond the customer's wallets. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon had created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customers' wallets.

Shoppers Had to Travel to Stores to Discover Goods and Buy Things Before Amazon

Data in Table 7 show that 34 (30.6%) agreed and 24 (21.6%) strongly agreed, totaling 58(52.2%), to the statement that shoppers had to travel to stores to discover goods and buy things before Amazon. However, 23 (20.7%) disagreed, as well as 26 (23.4%) strongly disagreed, totaling 49 (44.1%), implying that shoppers need not travel to stores to discover goods and buy things before Amazon. Of the respondents, 4 (3.6%) were undecided on whether shoppers had to travel to stores to discover goods and buy things before Amazon. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that shoppers had to travel to stores to discover goods and buy things before Amazon.

Null Hypothesis 1: Economic Globalization Does Not Have Any Significant Effect on the Business Strategies Used in Amazon

Correlation Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies Used in Amazon

This study assumed that economic globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon, and to prove whether this was true, Table 8 shows the correlation results.

Table 8

Results of the Correlation Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies Used in Amazon

		Economic Globalization	Business Strategies
	Pearson Correlation	1	.081
Economic Globalization	Sig. (2-tailed)		.398
	<i>N</i>	111	111
	Pearson Correlation	.081	1
Business Strategies	Sig. (2-tailed)	.398	
	<i>N</i>	111	111

Table 8 shows results of a two-tailed relation between economic globalization and business strategies in Amazon, and the Pearson correlation shows that in every single change in economic globalization, there are .081 changes in business strategies, hence, bringing the significance at .398 greater than *P*-value (0.05), and this means that economic globalization has a negative effect on business strategies in Amazon. The study results agree with the stated null hypothesis that economic globalization does not significantly affect the business strategies used in Amazon.

Histogram Illustrating the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

Considering the correlation results, which indicate a negative effect between economic and business strategies use at Amazon, this study demonstrates how the relationship appears in a histogram shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

The curve's movement in Figure 4 shows an upward shift in the relationship between economic globalization and business strategies from 20.00 to 25.00 and a slope in the curve starting from 25.00 to 35.00. However, there are externalities of some respondents' frequencies that have gone above the curve, resulting in low levels in the relationship between economic globalization and business strategies.

Objective 2: To Set the Relationship Between Technological Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon

To set the relationship between technology globalization and business strategies of Amazon, this study attempted to ask several questions from which answers were derived concluding whether technology globalization had a positive or a significant negative relationship

with business strategies in Amazon. Table 9 illustrates results on the relationship between technology globalization and the business strategies of Amazon.

Table 9

Relationship Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon

Statements on the Relationship Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Amazon’s goal is to become a one-stop shop for all online purchases.	F %	19 17.21	21 18.9	6 5.4	39 35.1	26 23.4
Amazon continues to invest in technologies that will further consolidate its grip on e-commerce.	F %	30 27.0	19 17.1	1 0.9	42 37.8	19 17.1
Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer.	F %	22 19.8	16 14.4	4 3.6	43 38.7	26 23.4
Amazon has created an internal experimentation platform to evaluate improvements to its workers, websites, and products.	F %	20 18.0	12 10.8	2 1.8	45 40.5	32 28.8
Amazon records every move or customer click.	F %	31 27.9	15 13.5	4 3.6	43 38.7	18 16.2

(continued)

Statements on the Relationship Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in Amazon.	F	15	32	4	39	21
	%	18.9	20.7	1.8	40.5	18.9
Changes in the consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect.	F	21	23	2	45	20
	%	18.9	20.7	1.8	40.5	18
Amazon has relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases.	F	21	23	2	36	29
	%	18.9	20.7	1.8	32.4	26.1
Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work.	F	28	25	1	36	21
	%	25.2	22.5	0.9	32.4	18.9
		Yes	Not at all	Sometime	Rarely	When necessary
Amazon motivates its workers.	F	25	24	25	23	14
	%	22.5	21.6	22.5	20.7	12.6

Note. N = 111

Amazon’s Goal Is to Become a One-Stop Shop for Online Purchases

Following Table 9, results show that 39 (35.1%) agreed and 26 (23.4%) strongly agree, totaling 65 (58.5%), to the statement that Amazon’s goal is to become a one-stop shop for all

online purchases. However, 21 (18.9%) disagreed, as well as 19 (17.1%) strongly disagreed, totaling 40 (36%), implying that Amazon's goal is not to become a one-stop shop for all online purchases. In addition, 6 (5.4%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon's goal is to be a one-stop shop for all online purchases. This means that most respondents indicated that Amazon's goal is to become a one-stop shop for all online purchases.

Amazon Continues to Invest in Technologies That Will Further Consolidate Its Grip on E-Commerce

The results from Table 9 show that 42 (37.8%) agreed and 19 (17.1%) strongly agree, totaling 61 (54.9%), to the statement that Amazon continues to invest in technologies that will further consolidate its grip on e-commerce. However, 30 (27%) disagreed, as well as 19 (17.1%) strongly disagreed, totaling 49 (44.1%), implying that Amazon does not continue to invest in technologies that will further consolidate its grip on e-commerce. Of the respondents, 1 (0.9%) was undecided on whether Amazon invests in technologies that consolidate its grip on e-commerce. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon continues to invest in technologies that will further consolidate its grip on e-commerce.

Amazon Has Different Methods of Delivering Ordered Goods to the Consumer

The results in Table 9 show that 43 (38.7%) agreed and 26 (23.4%) strongly agreed, totaling 69 (62.1%), that Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer. However, 16 (14.4%) disagreed, as well as 22 (19.8%) strongly disagreed, totaling 38 (34.2%), suggesting that Amazon does not have different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer. Therefore, 4 (3.6%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer. This means that the majority of

the respondents indicated that Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer.

Amazon Has Created an Internal Experimentation Platform to Evaluate Improvements to Its Workers, Websites, and Products

The results in Table 9 show that 45 (40.5%) agreed and 32 (28.8%) strongly agreed, totaling 77 (69.3%), to the statement that Amazon has created an internal experimentation platform that it uses to evaluate improvements to their workers, websites, and products. However, 12 (10.8%) disagreed, as well as 20 (18%) strongly disagreed, totaling 32 (28.8%), implying Amazon has not created an internal experimentation platform that it uses to evaluate improvements to its workers, websites, and products. In addition, 2 (1.8%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon has created an internal experimentation platform to evaluate improvements to its workers, websites, and products. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon had created an internal experimentation platform that it uses to evaluate improvements to its workers, websites, and products.

Amazon Records Every Move or Clicks a Visitor Makes

The results in Table 9 show that 43 (38.7%) agreed and 18 (16.2%) strongly agreed, totaling 61 (54.9%), to the statement that Amazon records every move or click a visitor makes. However, 15 (13.5%) disagreed, as well as 31 (27.9%) strongly disagreed, totaling 46 (41.4%), implying that Amazon does not record every move or click a visitor makes. Of the respondents, 4 (3.5%) were undecided on whether Amazon records every move or click a visitor makes. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon records every move or click a visitor makes.

Globalization Creates Many Benefits and Opportunities in Amazon

The results in Table 9 show that 39 (35.1%) agreed and 21 (18.9%) strongly agreed, totaling 60 (54%), to the statement that globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in Amazon. However, 32 (28.5%) disagreed, as well as 5 (13.5%) strongly disagreed, totaling 47 (42%), implying that globalization does not create many benefits and opportunities in the Amazon. Of the respondents, 4 (3.6%) were undecided on whether globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in the Amazon. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in Amazon.

Changes in Consumer Patterns Have Occurred as a Result of the Amazon Effect

The results in Table 9 show that 45 (40.5%) agreed and 20 (18.0%) strongly agreed, totaling 65 (58.5%), to the statement that changes in the consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect. However, 23 (20.7%) disagreed, as well as 21 (18.9%) strongly disagreed, totaling 44 (39.6%), implying that changes in consumer patterns have not occurred as a result of the Amazon effect. Of the respondents, 2 (1.8%) were undecided on whether changes in consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that changes in consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect.

Amazon Has Relied Heavily on Customer Loyalty and Repeat Purchases

Table 9 shows that 36 (32.4%) agreed and 29 (26.1%) strongly agreed, totaling 65 (58.5%), to the statement that Amazon has relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases. However, 23 (20.7%) disagreed, as well as 21 (18.9%) strongly disagreed, totaling 44 (39.6%), implying that Amazon has not relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases. Of the respondents, 2 (1.8%) were undecided on whether Amazon has relied heavily on customer

loyalty and repeat purchases. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon has relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases.

Amazon Has a Long-Standing Practice of Trying out Concepts Before Committing to the Ones That Work

Table 9 shows that 36 (32.4%) agreed and 21 (18.9%) strongly agree, totaling 57 (51.3%), to the statement that Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work. However, 25 (25.2%) disagreed, as well as 25 (22.5%) strongly disagreed, totaling 50 (47.7%), implying that Amazon does not have a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work. Of the respondents, 1 (0.9%) were undecided on whether Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work.

Amazon Motivates Its Workers

Table 9 shows results on whether Amazon motivates its workers, and 25 (22.5%) of the respondents indicated that Amazon motivates its workers sometimes, 25 (22.5%) admitted that Amazon motivates its workers, 24 (21.6%) denied that Amazon motivates its workers, 23 (20.7%) indicated that Amazon rarely motivates its workers, and 14 (12.6%) indicated that Amazon motivates its workers whenever it is necessary. The majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon motivates its workers. This implies that Amazon motivates its workers.

Null Hypothesis 2: Technology Globalization Does Not Significantly Affect the Business Strategies Used in Amazon

Correlation Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies Used in Amazon

This study assumed that technology globalization does not significantly affect the business strategies used in Amazon. To prove whether this was true, Table 10 shows the correlation results.

Table 10

Results of the Correlation Between Economic Globalization Business Strategies Used in Amazon

		Business Strategies	Technology Globalization
	Pearson Correlation	1	.081
Business Strategies	Sig. (2-tailed)		.774
	N	111	111
	Pearson Correlation	.028	1
Technology Globalization	Sig. (2-tailed)	.774	
	N	111	111

Table 10 shows results of a two-tailed correlation between technology globalization and business strategies in Amazon, and the Pearson correlation shows that in every single change in technology globalization, there are .081 changes in business strategies, bringing the significance at .028 less than P -value (0.05), and this means that technology globalization has a weak positive effect on business strategies in Amazon. The study results reject the stated null hypothesis that technology globalization does not significantly affect the business strategies used in Amazon and instead states that technology globalization significantly affects the business strategies used in Amazon.

Histogram Illustrating the Relationship Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

Considering the correlation results, which indicate a negative effect between technology globalization and business strategies use at Amazon, this study demonstrated the relationship in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Relationship Between Technology Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

The curve’s movement in Figure 5 shows an upward shift in the relationship between technology globalization and business strategies from 25.00 to 30.00 and a slope in the curve starting from 30.00 to 40.00. Nevertheless, there are externalities of some respondents’ frequencies that have gone above the curve, lowering the levels in the relationship between technological globalization and business strategies.

Objective 3: To Assess the Effect of Financial Globalization on the Business Strategies of Amazon

To assess the effect of financial globalization on the business strategies of Amazon, this study attempted to ask a number of questions from which answers were derived to conclude whether financial globalization had a positive or a significant adverse effect on the business strategy of Amazon. Table 11 illustrates the results on the effect of economic globalization on the business strategies of Amazon.

Table 11

Effect of Financial Globalization on the Business Strategies of Amazon

Statements on the Effect of Financial Globalization on Business Strategies of Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Amazon makes free deliveries to its prime members.	F	28	29	2	38	14
	%	25.2	26.1	1.8	34.2	12.6
Amazon’s success comes down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media.	F	23	22	2	42	22
	%	20.7	19.8	1.8	37.8	19.8

(continued)

Statements on the Effect of Financial Globalization on Business Strategies of Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Amazon's global expansion is intensifying.	F	23	28	2	40	18
	%	20.7	25.2	1.8	36.0	16.2
E-commerce marketing is all about the customers in Amazon.	F	29	31	3	28	20
	%	26.1	27.9	2.7	25.2	18
Amazon focuses on the customer.	F	21	33	2	34	21
	%	18.9	29.7	1.8	30.6	18.9
The workers' job security is certain.	F	21	25	5	40	20
	%	18.9	22.5	4.5	36	18
Amazon has put many resources in developing human resources.	F	19	26	2	45	19
	%	17.1	23.4	1.8	40.5	17.1
		satisfying	unsatisfying	Less satisfying	More satisfying	Not at all satisfying

(continued)

Statements on the	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Effect of Financial Globalization on Business Strategies of Amazon						
Amazon's price approach keeps customers coming back for more.	F	32	21	7	29	22
	%	28.8	18.9	6.3	26.1	19.8
		At all times	Most of the times	Sometimes	Rarely	Not at all
The bulk of the company's revenue continues to come through selling products online.	F	18	22	8	44	19
	%	16.2	19.8	7.2	36.6	17.1
		To everybody	To a few	To some	To none at all	Do not exist
Amazon has increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce.	F	24	30	21	16	20
	%	21.6	27	18.9	14.4	18

Note. N = 111

Amazon Makes Free Deliveries to Its Prime Members

Findings in Table 11 show that 38 (34.2%) agreed and 14 (12.6%) strongly agreed, totaling to 52 (46.8%), to the statement that Amazon makes free deliveries to its prime members. However, 29 (26.1%) disagreed, as well as 28 (25.2%) strongly disagreed, totaling 57 (51.3%), implying that Amazon does not make free deliveries to its prime members. Therefore, 2 (1.8%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon makes free deliveries to its prime members. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon does not make free deliveries to its prime members.

Amazon's Success Comes Down to the Fact That It Has Got the Right Time and Handling of Social Media

Results in Table 11 show that 42 (37.8%) agreed and 22 (19.8%) strongly agreed, totaling 64 (57.6%), to the statement that Amazon's success comes down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media. However, 22 (19.8%) disagreed, as well as 23 (20.7%) strongly disagreed, totaling 45 (40.5), implying that Amazon's success does not come down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media. In addition, 2 (1.8%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon's success comes down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media. This means that most respondents indicated that Amazon's success comes down to having the right time and handling of social media.

Amazon's Global Expansion Is Intensifying

Findings in Table 11 show 40 (36%) agreed and 18 (16.2%) strongly agreed, totaling 58 (52.2%), to the statement that Amazon's expansion is intensifying. However, 28 (25.2%) disagreed, as well as 23 (20.7%) strongly disagreed, totaling 51 (45.9%), implying that Amazon's global expansion is not intensifying. Of the respondents, 2 (1.8%) were undecided on

whether Amazon's global expansion is intensifying. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon's global expansion is intensifying.

E-Commerce Marketing Is All About the Customers in Amazon

Findings in Table 11 show that 28 (25.2%) agreed and 20 (18%) strongly agreed, totaling 48 (43.2%), to the statement that e-commerce marketing is all about the customers in Amazon. However, 31 (27.9%) disagreed, as well as 29 (26.1%) strongly disagreed, totaling 60 (54%), implying that e-commerce marketing is not all about the customers in Amazon. Of the respondents, 3 (2.7%) were undecided on whether e-commerce marketing is all about the customers in Amazon. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that e-commerce marketing is not all about the customers in Amazon.

The Workers' Job Security Is Certain

Findings in Table 11 show that 40 (36%) agreed and 20 (18%) strongly agreed, totaling 60 (54%), to the statement that the workers' job security is certain. However, 25 (22.5%) disagreed, as well as 21 (18.9%) strongly disagreed, totaling 46 (41.4%), implying that the workers' job security is not certain. Of the respondents, 5 (4.5%) were undecided on whether the workers' job security is certain. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that the workers' job security is certain.

Amazon's Price Approach Keeps Customers Coming Back for More

Results in Table 11 show that 32 (28.8%) indicated that Amazon's price approach keeps customers coming back for more is satisfying, 29 (26.1%) indicated more satisfying, 22 (19.8%) indicated not at all satisfying, 21 (18.9%) indicated unsatisfyingly, and 7 (6.3%) indicated less satisfying. Thus, most of the respondents in this study indicated that Amazon's price approach keeps customers coming back for more.

The Bulk of the Company's Revenue Continues to Come Through Selling Products Online

Data in Table 11 show that 44 (39.6%) indicated that the bulk of the company's revenue continues to come through selling products online rarely happens, 22 (19.8%) indicated most of the times, 19 (17.1%) indicated not at all, 18(16.2%) indicated at all time, and 8 (7.2%) indicated most of the time. Thus, most of the respondents indicated that most of the company's revenue comes from selling products online.

Amazon Has Increased Its Sales Numbers and Customers Through E-Commerce

According to results in Table 11, 30 (27%) indicated Amazon had increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce is clear to a few, 24 (21.6%) indicated that Amazon had increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce is clear to everybody, 21 (18.9%) indicated that Amazon had increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce is apparent to some, 20 (18%) indicated that Amazon had increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce do not exist, and 16 (14.4%) indicated that Amazon increased its sales numbers and customers through e-commerce are is clear to none at all. The majority of the respondents in this study indicated an increase in sales and customer base.

Null Hypothesis 3: Financial Globalization Does Not Have Any Significant Effect on Business Strategies Used in Amazon

This study assumed that financial globalization does significantly affect the business strategies used in Amazon, and to prove whether this was true, Table 12 shows the correlation results.

Table 12*Correlation Between Financial Globalization Strategies Used at Amazon*

		Business Strategies	Financial globalization
Business Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	-.355**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	<i>N</i>	111	111
Financial globalization	Pearson Correlation	-.355**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	<i>N</i>	111	111

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12 shows results of a two-tailed Pearson correlation between financial globalization and business strategies in Amazon; the correlation shows that in every single change in financial globalization, there are .355 changes in business strategies, bringing the significance at .000 less than the *P*-value (0.05). This means that financial globalization has a positive effect on business strategies in Amazon. The study results reject the stated null hypothesis that financial globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon and instead states that financial globalization significantly affects the business strategies used in Amazon.

Histogram Illustrating the Relationship Between Financial Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

Considering the correlation results indicating a negative effect between financial globalization and business strategies used at Amazon, this study demonstrates how the relationship appears in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Relationship Between Financial Globalization and Business Strategies at Amazon

The curve’s movement in Figure 6 shows the relationship between financial globalization and business strategies from 20.00 to 30.00 and a slope in the curve starting from 30.00 to 35.00. However, there are externalities. However, some respondent’s frequencies that have gone above the curve lower levels in the relationship between financial globalization and business strategies.

Objective 4: To Identify the Different Business Strategies Used by Amazon

Business strategies was the dependent variable of this study, and so this sought to identify the different business strategies used by Amazon. Several questions were asked to confirm whether there are different business strategies used by Amazon, as shown in Table 13.

Table 13

Different Business Strategies Used By Amazon

Statements on the Different Business Strategies Used by Amazon	F/%	Responses				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Amazon focuses on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business.	F %	23 20.7	31 27.9	6 5.4	33 29.7	18 16.2
Amazon concentrates on costing differences to determine the inefficiency of the business.	F %	25 22.5	25 22.5	2 1.8	37 33.3	22 19.8
Amazon prioritizes nature the of product to be sent on the market to the effectiveness of the business.	F %	28 25.2	16 14.4	3 2.7	37 33.3	27 24.3
Amazon looks at business growth and expansion to determine its image.	F %	22 19.8	27 24.3	6 5.4	34 30.6	22 19.8

Amazon Focuses on Adapting to Market Behaviors for the Effectiveness of the Business

Table 13 shows that 33 (29.7%) agreed and 18 (16.2%) strongly agreed, totaling 51 (45.9%), to the statement that Amazon focuses on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business. However, 31 (27.9%) disagreed, as well as 23 (20.7%) strongly disagreed, totaling 54 (48.6%), implying that changes in Amazon do not focus on adapting to market behaviors to effect liveness of the business. Of the respondents, 6 (5.4%) were undecided

on whether changes in Amazon focus on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that changes in Amazon focus on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business.

Amazon Concentrates on Costing Differences to Determine the Efficiency of the Business

Table 13 shows that 37 (33.3%) agreed and 22 (19.8%) strongly agreed, totaling 59 (53.1%), to the statement that Amazon concentrates on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business. However, 25 (22.5%) disagreed, as well as 25 (22.5%) strongly disagreed, totaling 50 (51%), implying that changes in Amazon do not concentrate on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business. Of the respondents, 2 (1.8%) were undecided on whether changes in Amazon concentrate on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon concentrates on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business.

Amazon Prioritizes the Nature of the Products to Be Sent on the Market for the Effectiveness of the Business

Table 13 shows that 37 (33.3%) agreed and 27 (24.3%) strongly agreed, totaling 64 (57.6%), to the statement that Amazon prioritizes the nature of the product to be sent on the market for the effectiveness of the business. However, 16 (14.4%) disagreed, as well as 28 (25.2%) strongly disagreed, totaling 44 (39.6%), implying that Amazon does not prioritize the nature of the product to be sent on the market for the effectiveness of the business. In addition, 3 (2.7%) of the respondents were undecided on whether Amazon prioritizes the nature of products to be sent on the market for the effectiveness of the business. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that changes in Amazon prioritize the nature of the product to be sent on the market for the effectiveness of the business.

Amazon Looks at Business Growth and Expansion to Determine Its Image

Table 13 shows that 34 (30.6%) agreed and 22 (19.8%) strongly agreed, totaling 56 (50.4%), to the statement that Amazon looks at business growth and expansion to determine its image. However, 27 (24.3%) disagreed, as well as 22 (19.8%) strongly disagreed, totaling 49 (44.1%), implying that Amazon does not look at business growth and expansion to determine its image. Of the respondents, 6 (5.4%) were undecided on whether Amazon looks at business growth and expansion to determine its image. This means that the majority of the respondents indicated that Amazon looks at business growth and expansion to determine its image.

Modal Summary Showing Predictors

This study examined the challenges of globalization on business strategies in Amazon U.S. The challenges of globalization on business strategies specified under study were economic, technology, and financial, which were tested in the field using different questions, and results were identified as shown. However, it was in the interest of this study to identify the most outstanding challenge that affects business strategies by finding out among the three which one predicted business strategies of Amazon. Table 14 shows the modal summary indicating the predictors.

Table 14

Modal Summary

Modal	R	R ²	Adjusted R Square	Std. An error of the Estimate
1	.355 ^a	.126	.118	2.63909

a. Predictors: (Constant), financial globalization

The modal summary above shows that financial globalization is predicted at $R = .355$, R Square = .126, with adjusted R Square at .118 on business strategies. This means that of the three examined challenges, only financial globalization was predicted, and this is an indicator that

Amazon suffers with more financial globalization challenges than economic and technological globalization challenges.

Excluded Variables

Considering the results on predictor variables in the modal summary (financial globalization), this study also was interested in identifying the excluded variables from the independent variable (globalization), and Table 15 shows the excluded variables.

Table 15

Excluded Variable

Modal	Beta In	<i>t</i>	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics Tolerance
1 Economic globalization	.128 ^b	1.421	.158	.136	.984
Technology globalization	-.037 ^b	-.404	.687	-.039	.968

a. Dependent Variable: business

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), financial

Table 15 shows study excluded variables and economic globalization was beta in at .128 with time interval at 1.421 at a significance at .158 greater than *P*-value (0.05), and collinearity statistics tolerance of the dependent variable (business strategies) was at .984. This means that economic globalization was excluded as one of the global challenges affecting the business strategies used by Amazon. Technology globalization also was at beta in -.037 with time interval at -.404 at significance at .687 greater than *P*-value (0.05), and collinearity statistics tolerance at .968. This means that technology globalization was excluded as one of the global challenges affecting the business strategies used by Amazon. Therefore, this study results show that economic and technological globalization challenges were excluded variables affecting business strategies used by Amazon, and indicators that Amazon business strategies used are not affected

by economic and technology globalization challenges but are affected by only financial globalization challenges.

Lead to Chapter 5

Chapter 4 presented and analyzed data from the field using the frequency tables and narratives from the qualitative data creating a gap in the need to discuss the related findings elsewhere by other researchers. Chapter 5 discusses the researcher's findings. In addition, summary, conclusions, and recommendations are also presented in line with the study objectives.

Chapter 5

Summary, Conclusion, Discussions, and Recommendation

This chapter focused on the study summary, conclusions, discussion, and recommendations, and guided the study objectives below.

Summary

This section focuses on a summary. The study aimed at examining the challenges of globalization on business strategies in the Amazon U.S. with specific objectives, namely:

- To establish the relationship between financial Globalization and business strategies in Amazon;
- To set the relationship between technological globalization and business strategies of Amazon;
- To assess the effect of Financial Globalization on the business strategies of Amazon; and
- To identify the different business strategies used by Amazon.

The study established globalization as the independent variable measured by financial, technology, and economics, and business strategy was the dependent variable indicated by product differentiation, cost strategy, market strategy, growth, and expansion. In addition, the study findings indicated that of the three examined globalization measurements (financial, technological, and economic), only financial globalization was predicted, and technological and economic globalization were excluded.

Demographic Findings

This study's demographic results showed that most of the respondents approached in this study were diploma holders. Additionally, the results by gender indicated male as the majority

being approached, part-time as the respondents' appointment status, and they belonged to Amazon devices and digital management.

Objective 1: To Establish the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon

This study established the relationship between economic globalization and business strategies in Amazon with a null hypothesis stating that economic globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon. The correlation results indicated that in a single change in economic globalization, there are .081 changes in business strategies, and economic globalization hurts business strategies with a significance at .393 greater than *P*-value (0.05). So, the findings agreed with the null hypothesis that economic globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon. However, there is a central response with qualitative findings, which suggested that economic globalization has a significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon.

Such findings were generated with the support of many questions, which showed the majority of responses indicated that economic globalization directly promotes growth in Amazon; globalization has increased job opportunities in Amazon; workers are using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents through economic globalization; Amazon can manage its international operations in more efficient ways; and Amazon has been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist. In addition, Amazon has created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customer's wallets, and shoppers had to travel to stores to discover what goods were available and buy things before Amazon.

Objective 2: To Set the Relationship Between Technological Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon

This study set the relationship between technological globalization and business strategies of Amazon with a null hypothesis that technology globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon. The correlation results indicated that in every single change in technology globalization, there are .081 changes in business strategies, and technological globalization has a positive effect on business strategies with a significance at .028 less than P -value (0.05). So, the findings rejected the stated null hypothesis that technology globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon and instead stated that technology globalization significantly affects the business strategies used in Amazon. The qualitative results were also in line with the quantitative results.

Such findings were generated with the support of many questions, which showed the majority of the responses indicated that Amazon's goal is to become a one-stop shop for all online points of purchase, Amazon continues to invest in technologies that further consolidate its grip on e-commerce, Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer, and Amazon has created an internal experimentation platform that it uses to evaluate improvements to its workers, websites, and products. Amazon records every move or click a visitor makes. Globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in Amazon. Changes in consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect. Changes have relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases. Amazon motivates its workers. This also implies that Amazon motivates its workers, and Amazon has a long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work.

Objective 3: To Assess the Effect of Financial Globalization on the Business Strategies of Amazon

This study assessed the effect of financial globalization on the business strategies of Amazon with a null hypothesis stating that financial globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies in Amazon. The correlation results indicated that in every single change in financial globalization, there are .355 changes in business strategies. Furthermore, financial globalization positively affects business strategies with a significance at .000 less than P -value (0.05). Therefore, the findings rejected the stated null hypothesis that financial globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon and instead stated that financial globalization significantly affects the business strategies used in Amazon. The qualitative results were also in line with the quantitative results.

Such findings were generated with the support of many questions, which showed a majority of responses indicated that Amazon makes free deliveries to its Prime members, Amazon's success comes down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media, Amazon's global expansion is intensifying, the e-commerce marketing is not all about the customers in the Amazon, the workers' job security is specific, Amazon has put many resources into developing human resources, and the bulk of the company's revenue continues to come through selling products online rarely happens.

Objective 4: To Identify the Different Business Strategies Used by Amazon

This study was interested in identifying the different business strategies used by Amazon and the findings showed that the qualitative and quantitative results concur, with each agreeing that Amazon has used more product differentiation as its business strategy than other business strategies, followed by cost strategy, growth, expansion, and market strategy. Such findings were

generated with the support of several questions, which showed a majority of the responses indicated that Amazon focuses on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business, Amazon concentrates on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business, Amazon prioritizes the nature of the product to be sent on the market for the effectiveness of the business, and the Amazon looks at business growth and expansion to determine its image.

Conclusions

The study concluded that of the three measurements of globalization, only financial globalization causes a positive effect on business strategies used by Amazon, and so challenges of financial globalization affect the business strategy of an organization. However, one should not undermine the challenges of technological globalization.

Objective 1: To Establish the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon

This study concluded that economic globalization does not affect business strategies in Amazon, and so challenges of economic globalization do not affect the business strategies of an organization. However, one should disregard that economic globalization is among the factors influencing an organization's choice of business strategy.

Objective 2: To Set the Relationship Between Technological Globalization and Business Strategies of Amazon

This study concluded that technological globalization challenges lightly affect the business strategies of Amazon. This is because this study found a significant positive effect of technological globalization on the business strategies of Amazon. However, technological globalization affects business strategies combined with financial globalization.

Objective 3: To Assess the Effect of Financial Globalization on the Business Strategies of Amazon

This study concluded that financial globalization challenges affect the business strategies of Amazon. Furthermore, it is established that with only financial globalization challenges, the choice and the operation of the business strategies used by the organization is negatively affected and or may lead to a failure of successful business strategies used by the organization, which may later lead to the downfall of the business.

Objective 4: To identify the Different Business Strategies Used by Amazon

This study concluded that the most effective business strategy used by Amazon is product differentiation. However, other business strategies, including cost strategy, market strategy, growth, and expansion should not be undermined, as they can also be adopted, depending on an organization's choice.

General Conclusion

The study concluded that globalization does affect business strategies; however, technological and economic globalization were ruled out as factors influencing business strategies in Amazon. Therefore, financial globalization was assessed to be the primary participant in influencing the different business strategies used by Amazon.

Discussions

Objective 1: To Establish the Relationship Between Economic Globalization and Business Strategies in Amazon

Economic globalization does not affect business strategies in Amazon and so challenges of economic globalization do not affect the business strategies of an organization. This agrees with notions about economic globalization stated by Jain (2012), who associated economic

globalization with technological advancements, which have improved e-commerce globally. The writer stated that economic globalization amplified by global technology increases the rates of trade of goods and services provided by companies such as Amazon. Therefore, since Amazon is dependent on online sellers of goods and services, technological changes influence involvement in economic globalization. However, Jain (2012) stated economic globalization creates stiff competition, increases tax bases, and others across borders. This might affect companies such as Amazon to define a common business strategy that might apply globally.

This study's qualitative results indicate otherwise and generally state that economic globalization has a significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon. However, the different respondents raised different opinions.

One of the senior managers in Amazon Devices and Digital Management said:

Economic globalization has made Amazon changes in the way it operates its business strategies, and that is one of the reasons why the company is developing at high speed so that economic globalization can cause a positive effect on business strategies. (R₆)

On the line managers at Robotics and Project Kuiper said, "Economic globalization has a positive relationship with business strategies because Amazon has focused on the global economy to assess its business strategies" (R₇).

One the of the lower staff at Amazon Worldwide consumers said, "I have seen Amazon grow much with the influence of economic globalization for the last five years; economic globalization indeed causes a positive effect on business strategies" (R₈).

Therefore, even though native results agree with the stated null hypothesis that economic globalization does not have any significant effect on the business strategies used in Amazon, it is a unanimous conclusion that this is true since the detailed results collected from the interviews

suggest otherwise, which creates a doubt in the stated hypothesis and gives allowance to the alternative hypothesis that, instead, rejects the null hypothesis and states that economic globalization has significant effects on the business strategies used in Amazon.

Objective 2: To Set the Relationship Between Technological Globalization and Business

Strategies of Amazon

Technological globalization challenges lightly affect the business strategies of Amazon. This agrees with Kaushal (2018), whose assertion on technological globalization implied that setting up a website and providing items or services to the world does not suffice to conduct business across national borders. Other firms only think about globalization in adopting specific ICTs, such as the Internet and e-commerce (Manshady, 2012). Such comments and assertions by other researchers indicate technological globalization challenges affect business strategies used by an organization. Therefore, this study confirms that technological globalization affects the business strategies of an organization.

Objective 3: To Assess the Effect of Financial Globalization on the Business Strategies of Amazon

This study concluded that financial globalization challenges among the measurements of globalization studies (financial, economic, and technological) highly affected business strategies used. Therefore, it is concluded that financial globalization among the studied measurements of globalization caused a positive effect on business strategies. This agrees with Manshady and Totonchi (2012), who noted that because of globalization, companies are incurring more capital investments in areas such as technology and stated that as a result of globalization demands, financial constraints arise for the company to adapt to, which makes it hard for the company to identify the most effective business strategy. Further still, the qualitative responses confirmed the

quantitative results that financial globalization challenges affect business strategies. For example, one of the senior managers said, “A company suffering from the financial challenges cannot cope with global financial challenges that call for massive investments in things like technology and human resources, among others” (R₁₇). Therefore, this study’s findings prove that financial globalization challenges negatively affect business strategies used by the organization.

Objective 4: To Identify the Different Business Strategies Used by Amazon

The most effective business strategy used by Amazon is product differentiation. This study was interested in identifying the different business strategies used by Amazon and the findings showed that the qualitative and quantitative results concur, with each agreeing that Amazon has used more product differentiation as its business strategy than other business strategies, followed by cost strategy, growth, expansion, and market strategy. Such findings were generated with the support of many questions, which showed the majority of responses indicate that changes in Amazon focus on adapting to market behaviors for the effectiveness of the business, changes in Amazon concentrate on costing differences to determine the efficiency of the business, changes in Amazon prioritize the nature of the product to be sent on the mark for the effectiveness of the business, and changes in Amazon look at business growth and expansion to determine its image.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following. Amazon should focus on the financial globalization challenges by opening avenues for new investors to invest in Amazon. This can be done by selling off some shares to accumulate more share capital that can be used to invest at a global level. This will enable the company to build the financial capacity that enables it to align

with the increasing global financial demands and will open up flexibility in the choice of business strategy to be used.

Amazon should adopt other strategies of financial accumulation, such as making partnerships with complementary businesses across the world to enable it to reduce the gravity of fulfilling the global financial challenges and, instead, manage the challenges with partners. This will ease the issue of financial globalization, which is manageable as a team and not as a single entity. This can be done by signing a memorandum of understanding with potential and willing complementary businesses.

Amazon should devise a service outsourcing strategy to reduce the costs incurred in managing the financial globalization challenges. This helps in relieving the burden of direct managing financial globalization, but it can manage through the outsourced company. This can be done by identifying services companies that can provide essentials to Amazon. It can hire the hiring companies through bidding processes and those will work on Amazon's behalf.

Areas of Further Study

Further study can be done on the effect of global technological changes on the business strategy to assess the changes in technology on whether to maintain the same business strategy for effective business operations globally.

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APPENDIX A

Questionnaire

Dear Participant,

You have been selected to participate in this critical study designed to discover *the challenges of Globalization on Business Strategies in a modern organization - a case study of the Amazon.*

You are therefore requested to feel free and provide the information required as honestly as possible. Please note that all answers are essential, and there is no wrong or correct answer.

What is most important are your views on this subject.

Privacy is critical to us, and the information you provide will be treated with the highest confidentiality; all responses will remain confidential, and anonymity will be ensured.

Thank you for participating in this critical study.

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A: TICK WHERE APPROPRIATE

1. What is your qualification?

- (a) Certificate
- (b) Diploma Holder
- (c) B.A. Degree
- (d) B.Sc. Degree
- (e) B.A. Postgraduate
- (f) B.Sc. Postgraduate
- (g) Master's Degree
- (h) PhD
- (i) Any other Specify

2. What is your gender?

- (a) Male
- (b) Female
- (c) Transgender
- (d) Gay/Lesbian

4. What is the status of your appointment?

- (a) Part-time
- (b) Full time
- (c) Per diem
- (d) Agency

5. To which of the Amazon Corporation's five key divisions or business units do you belong?

- a) Amazon Web Services
- b) Worldwide consumer
- c) Amazon Devices and Digital Management
- d) Amazon Videos and studios
- e) Robotics and Project Kuiper

SECTION B: TICK WHERE APPROPRIATE

The effect of economic globalization on the Business strategies used in Amazon, US

6. Economic Globalization directly promotes growth in the Amazon.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

7. Globalization has increased job opportunities in the Amazon.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

8. Workers are using digital platforms to learn, find work, and showcase their talents.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

9. Through globalization, Amazon can manage its international operations in more efficient ways.

(a) Strongly Disagree

(b) Disagree

(c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

10. Amazon has been recognized as one of the most successful companies to exist.

(a) Strongly Disagree

(b) Disagree

(c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

11. Amazon has a raft of procedures to guide its disparate team

(a) Strongly Disagree

(b) Disagree

(c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

12. Amazon has created economic ripple effects that go beyond the customer's wallets.

(a) Strongly Disagree

- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

13. Shoppers had to travel to stores to discover what and buy things before Amazon.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

14. list down some challenges of globalization to the Amazon

.....

.....

SECTION C: TICK WHERE APPROPRIATE

The relationship that exists between Technological globalization and business strategies used in Amazon

15. Amazon’s goal is to become a one-stop-shop for all online purchases.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

16. Amazon continues to invest in technologies that will further consolidate its grip on e-

commerce.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

17. Amazon has different methods of delivering ordered goods to the consumer.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

18. Amazon motivates its workers

- (a) Yes
- (b) Not at all.
- (c) Sometimes
- (d) Rarely
- (e) When necessary

19. Amazon has created an internal experimentation platform to evaluate improvements to their workers, websites, and products.,

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided

- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
21. Amazon records every move or click a visitor makes.
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
22. Globalization creates many benefits and opportunities in the Amazon.
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
23. Changes in the consumer patterns have occurred as a result of the Amazon effect
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
24. Amazon has relied heavily on customer loyalty and repeat purchases.
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree

- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

25. Amazon has the long-standing practice of trying out concepts before committing to the ones that work.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

26. What suggestion would you give to Amazon to improve the customer base in the different parts of the world?

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SECTION D

Globalization and Business strategies used in Amazon.

34. Amazon’s price approach keeps customers coming back for more.

- (a) Satisfying
- (b) Unsatisfying
- (c) Less satisfying
- (d) More satisfying
- (e) Not at all satisfying.

35. Amazon makes free deliveries to its prime members

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree

36. The bulk of the company’s revenue continues to come through selling products online.

- (a) At all times
- (b) Most of the time
- (c) Sometimes
- (d) Rarely
- (e) Not at all

37. Amazon has increased their sales numbers and customers through e-commerce.

- (a) To every body
- (b) To a few
- (c) To some
- (d) To none at all
- (e) Do not exist

38. Amazon’s success comes down to the fact that it has got the right time and handling of social media.

- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree

- (e) Strongly agree
39. The Amazon's global expansion is intensifying.
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
40. E-commerce marketing is all about the customers in the Amazon
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
41. Amazon focuses in the customer.
- (a) (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided
- (d) Agree
- (e) Strongly agree
42. The workers' job security is certain
- (a) Strongly Disagree
- (b) Disagree
- (c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

43. Amazon has put a lot of resource in developing human resource

(a) Strongly Disagree

(b) Disagree

(c) Undecided

(d) Agree

(e) Strongly agree

44. List other business strategies used by the Amazon in its online transactions.

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.....

APPENDIX B

Interview Guide

Interview guide for senior and middle line managers and selected lower staff at Amazon.

Looking at; the challenges of globalization on business strategies in a modern organization - a case study amazon business

Dear respondent:

My name is SAMSON OGOLA. I am currently studying to write a dissertation as a requirement for the Doctor of Business Administration award of William Howard Taft University. You have been selected to participate in this study because of the importance of your position in this company. The information you provide will only be used for this study and will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Kindly help me generate solutions to the following questions.

Do I have your consent to interview you and record it?

Yes No

Business strategies in Amazon.

- 1) Which Amazon cooperation do you work for?
- 2) How is business conducted in your area of work?
- 3) Does this Amazon cooperation prioritize its business strategy by product differentiation, market dynamics, cost of production, and growth and expansion?
- 4) If any of the mentioned above, how quickly does it help the business reach its set goals?
- 5) Could globalization economic, technology, or financial factors hinder this business from reaching its goal through the identified and used business strategy?
- 6) If yes, how do you think this happens?

Thank you,

Objective one: To establish the relationship between financial Globalization and business strategies in the Amazon

- 1) Could there be a relationship between financial globalization and the business strategy used by Amazon?
- 2) If yes, what could be the relationship between financial globalization and business strategy?
- 3) How do you think Amazon has managed to utilize financial globalization to reach the set business strategy?
- 4) Could financial globalization stand out for Amazon to enable it to select an effective business strategy?
- 5) If yes, why do you think this could be possible?

Objective two: To set the relationship between technological globalization and business strategies of the Amazon

- 1) Could there be a relationship between technological globalization and the business strategy used by Amazon?
- 2) If yes, what could be the relationship between technological globalization and business strategy?
- 3) How do you think Amazon has managed to utilize technological globalization to reach the set business strategy?
- 4) Could technological globalization stand out for Amazon to enable it to select an effective business strategy?
- 5) If yes, why do you think this could be possible?

Objective three: To assess the effect of economic Globalization on the business strategies of

Amazon.

- 1) Could there be a relationship between economic globalization and the business strategy used by Amazon?
- 2) If yes, what could be the relationship between economic globalization and business strategy?
- 3) How do you think Amazon has managed to utilize economic globalization to reach the set business strategy?
- 4) Could economic globalization stand out for Amazon to enable it to select an effective business strategy?
- 5) If yes, why do you think this could be possible?

APPENDIX C

IRB Approval

IRB APPROVAL

Name of Candidate: **Ogola Samson**

Dissertation or Major Practical Project Title:

**THE CHALLENGES OF GLOBALIZATION ON BUSINESS STRATEGIES IN MODERN
ORGANISATION - A CASE STUDY OF THE AMAZON BUSINESS**

Date of Application: **07/26/2021**

Application Type (The IRB Committee makes this determination):

Expedited

Application Status (The IRB Committee makes this determination):

Approved

The candidate-researcher understands and agrees to maintain the confidentiality of any entity agreeing to assist with providing data, to obtain informed consent from any human participants in the study, and to retain and safeguard written consents and the data for a period of five years from all entities, presenting copies to William Howard Taft University, the participants, and authoritative bodies when appropriate.

IRB Representative Signature

Date

NOTE: The completed and signed form should be submitted to student_support@taftu.edu by the IRB Representative.

APPENDIX D

Informed Consent letter

Samson Ogola
[REDACTED]

Amazon.com Inc.
Office of VP Devices and Digital Management
410 Terry Avenue, North
Seattle, WA 98109

06/20/2021

Dear Lisa

Globalization is a natural process that arises from the generalization of the nature and method of production, which is a developing and faster process. The advancement of science and technology and the Globalization of markets for goods and services have resulted in the internationalization and Globalization of economic and financial developments. Globalization is defined as a process that leads to the greater economic integration of national economies, fragmentation of the world economy, and the international economy. It is also defined as opening national economies by removing economic and financial boundaries and transforming them into a global economic and financial. Amazon is a leader in Globalization, has been selected for this study dubbed "*The Challenges of Globalization on Business Strategies in Modern Organizations - A Case Study of the Amazon.*"

I am a doctoral student at William Howard Taft University researching the Challenges of Globalization on business strategies in modern organizations - a case study of Amazon. This letter is an invitation for your contribution to my research. I am therefore asking for permission to proceed with the study. As part of the research process, I will be sharing interview questionnaires to randomly selected managers and employees at amazon, amazon devices, and Digital management. Filling the questionnaire will only take a few minutes of their time. The respondents will complete the enclosed questionnaire assessing Challenges of Globalization on Business Strategies in Modern Organizations - A Case Study of the Amazon. The respondents will complete and submit the questionnaire within 14 days. All responses will remain confidential, and anonymity will be ensured.

This study aims at examining the challenges of Globalization on business strategies in Amazon. Specifically, the study seeks to: Establish the relationship between financial Globalization and business strategies in Amazon, set the relationship between technological Globalization and business strategies of Amazon finally assess the effect of Financial Globalization on the business strategies of Amazon.

The cost of the study will be undertaken by the researcher, and amazon will not be financing any part of this research, although the support is highly appreciated. The final report will be submitted to Amazon with recommendations aimed at proposing improvements to overall organization performance in the global environment. Once I have a go-ahead from you, I will share the questionnaires that I intend to use for the study for review before we can send it out to different people in the organization, who will complete the questionnaire assessing challenges of Globalization on business strategies in the Amazon.

The study is for academic purposes only and will be carried out between July- September 2021; The responses will contribute to this timely research about the challenges of Globalization on business strategies in the Amazon. A summary of the study, findings, and recommendations will be mailed to your office upon completing this study.

I greatly appreciate your organization's participation in this research. Would you please let me know if you have any questions concerning this study or the enclosures? You may reach me at [REDACTED] or by e-mail at [REDACTED].

Please feel free to reach out to me should you have any other questions.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Samson Ogola', with a stylized initial 'S'.

Samson Ogola

APPENDIX E

Approval of Dissertation Proposal

Doctoral Student: Samson Ogola

The Dissertation Committee of the above named Doctoral Student has met and reviewed the Dissertation Proposal entitled:

The challenges of globalization on business strategies in modern organization - a case study of the amazon business

The committee has determined that the proposed dissertation is likely to:

1. Make a significant contribution to the field of knowledge;
2. Demonstrate the Student’s ability to perform independent research;
3. Contain material worthy of publication in a form appropriate to the discipline.

We recommend acceptance of this proposal. It contains all appropriate content and forms.

Dissertation Proposal Requires IRB Review: ___ Yes ___ No

(If the Dissertation Proposal requires IRB review, a signed IRB Approval must be obtained before beginning the study).

Doctoral Committee Members

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____

Doctoral Committee Chair

_____ **Date**

Completed Forms should be submitted the Academic Dean through the Dissertation student’s chair

APPENDIX G

Certificate of Time Expended

I certify under penalty of perjury that I expended approximately ____ hours in connection with completing the research and writing of the dissertation proposal. I further certify that I personally completed the research and writing the dissertation proposal I submitted to the University and said dissertation proposal is the product of my efforts.

Signature of Student: _____

Student # ____8384_____

Date: ____09/20/2021_____

I declare that I am the person who executed the foregoing *Certificate of Time Expended*, which execution is my act and deed.

APPENDIX H

Student Declaration Form

STUDENT DECLARATION FORM

I, Samson, A. Ogola, hereby certify all material submitted to William Howard Taft University in connection with the Dissertation was the result of my personal efforts. I hereby authorize the University to make my dissertation in full or in part, available to interested parties including but not limited to past, present, and future Taft students and faculty, state licensing agencies, and accrediting bodies. I further authorize my dissertation to be posted on the University's website. Any costs associated with dissemination under this paragraph shall be the responsibility of the University.

However, the University shall not, without my prior written consent, use my dissertation for any commercial purposes other than the purposes stated in the previous paragraph. Commercial purpose, for purposes of this declaration, means any distribution for which the University receives a fee or royalty.

Signature of Student:

Date: 09/21/2021

Student # 8384

THIS DECLARATION MUST BE NOTARIZED

State of _____ County of _____

Personally appeared before me this ____ day of _____ 20__, the above named _____, to me known as the individual who executed the above declaration and being first sworn, stated upon oath and penalty of perjury that he or she has read the above statements and such statements are true and correct.

Notary Seal

Notary Signature

APPENDIX I

Statement of Consent

I have read the information herein; have asked questions and received answers; and have received a copy of this form. By signing below, I consent to participate in this study.

Signature of committee member/instructor

Date

Candidate/Researcher Statement

All information contained herein is accurate. I have provided the participant with a copy of this form.

09/20/2021

Candidate/Researcher Signature

Date